

Basic functions of the structure of evolutionary cycles of mathematical genetics and physics

Organic and non-organic phases of Global Matter

Author

Alexander Ivanovich Khripkov

Independent researcher (1990 - 2023)

Private person

Research does not and did not have funding

Novosibirsk, Russia

E-mail: khripkov54@inbox.ru

• Resume

Thematic values of numerical definitions of subject data in various fields of science lead to the manipulation of digital codes of known physical, chemical, biological, genetic and other quantities. In principle, each scientific substantiation contains, to one degree or another, a quantitative, qualitative characteristic of comparison or content. Thus, the language of natural numbers, as well as mathematical operations, can be accompanied by any definition in any terminology. In this text, the author does not use well-known terms related to the main scientific directions. In this text, the numbers speak for themselves. Any combination of orders or compositions of complex numerical structures presented in this text has its own logical meaning. Any paradox of numerical combinations is an algorithm for the real values of numbers. All this speaks of an undeniable and independent Law - the Law of Consciousness of natural numbers, which determines the fundamental scientific data.

• Keywords

Number theory, number structure, natural numbers, number series, number order, number function, number event, number field, degree of movement, number reorientation, numerical data, database, scientific programs, artificial intelligence, number integration, number values, degree of freedom, paradoxes of numbers, fundamental data, unity of numbers. functional connection, phases of functions, sequences of functions, order of functions, limits of functions, functional transitions, tensor functions, mathematical physics, mathematical genetics, nuclear functions, neutrinos, quantum.

•Preface

The study of the process of periodic contraction and expansion, the functional structure of the unit charge of [Hydrogen \(page 31\)](#), as an expression of the concentration of the contour of space, made it possible to establish the limits of the periods of the elementary functions of "expansion" and "compression" of this structure. As a result, the function of the "expansion" process became the reason for the formation of a binary cycle, the periodic interaction of the functional expression of the opposite limits of "compression" and "expansion" of this space charge structure.

From the point of view of mathematics, the established cause corresponds to the paradox when one is not equal to one [$1 \neq 1$].

This inequality is determined by the content of all possible quantitative compositions in the structure of each mathematical symbol. In this case, the tensor periodic orders of the compositions of quantitative complexes determine the value of the limits of the sequential formation of functional structures of genetic, biological, nuclear and chemical symbols.

The conditions for maintaining the value of the primary volume ($\pi/6$) divide the structure of the unit into two projections, internal and external content:

[$1 - 0.523598776 = 0.476401224$], (52% and 48%) respectively.

With corrections for physical mass, these projections correspond to the content of Sodium ($_{11}\text{Na}^{21}$).

This definition of the volume unit structure ($\pi / 6$) corresponds to:

$$[2 + 3 + 6 = 11] \text{ or } [2^{-1} + 3^{-1} + 6^{-1} = 1].$$

In its turn: $[11^{-1} = \text{pH}^1]$. The proposed data were established according to the author's method. In particular, the definition of each nucleon of a chemical element occurs according to the state of stable mass numbers.

For sodium, this number is: $m = 22.9898$.

$$\text{Its nucleon: } [nykl = (22.9898 / 23) = 0.999556522].$$

Next, the limit projection exchange function:

$$((A+B)/A)^{-1} = 0.49965561 \text{ and } ((A+B)/B)^{-1} = 0.50034439$$

$$\text{Here: } A = mp(1.00727647); B = mn(1.008665012).$$

In case of opposite phases: $[((A+B)/A)^{-1} + ((A+B)/B)^{-1}] = 1$, the shift value in the functional structure of the nucleon is applied: $nykl - ((A+B)/A)^{-1}$ and $nykl - ((A+B)/B)^{-1}$.

Thus, the value of the projections of the main functions of protons and neutrons - the limits of "compression" and "expansion" is determined by the "shift" due to the number of the nucleon.

Under the conditions of the structure (${}_{Z}N\alpha^{21}$) the number of functional projections:

$$fmp = 0.523465903, fmn = 0.476090619.$$

• Introduction

The order of distribution of chemical elements of the periodic table of D. I. Mendeleev is based on the sequence of the charge number of the nuclear symbol. In this definition, the mass number, which contains the ratio of the numbers of protons and the numbers of neutrons, as a rule, basically coincides with this periodicity in the composition of stable nuclei.

Under the conditions of the composition of all the isotopes of this table, the usual order of chemical elements significantly and qualitatively changes the content of its sequence. In this case, we are talking about a [mathematical](#) cyclic table (**page 35**) of known isotopes.

The numerical sequence of this order depends on the ratio of the charge number to the mass number of the chemical element. Thus, the ratio of the number of protons to the number of neutrons of each isotope determines its place in the general mass system of nuclear symbols. In turn, the isobars of mass definitions constitute their own orders of mass complexes. Naturally, under the conditions of physical definitions, the compositions of these orders depend on the types and decay periods of unstable nuclei. Consequently, determining the causes and conditions of these data also depend on the quantitative interactions of protons and neutrons in the structure of these nuclei. The proposed method, based on research data, ordinal compositions of mass values, makes it possible to determine various conditions for various reasons for the formation and maintenance of systems of mass structures.

The main condition for all possible causes is the periodic state of the numerical values of protons and neutrons in the structure of the nucleon. In this case, the determination of the actual mathematical numbers of protons and neutrons, in each isotope, is perceived as the extreme values of the general state of the content of the mass number. These extreme values are presented as the limits of the functional processes of "compression" and "expansion". Thus, any value of the proton number is the limit of "compression" in the composition of the nucleon. In turn, any value of a neutron determines the limit of "expansion" of the functional (numerical) structure of this nucleon. Thus, the phase of the functional exchange, between the given limits of the numerical structure of the nucleon, does not affect the external content of the mass number of this isotope, according to the principle of the general law of conservation of mass. While the internal content of the numerical structure of the presented isotope significantly changes its physical, chemical, biological characteristics relative to the main functions of the numerical composition of this element. The reason for such definitions is the ratio of three functional values in the composition of the structure of an individual isotope. These are the value (fragment number) of the proton function, the value (fragment number) of the neutron function, and the value (number of the bond event) - the difference of these values - the degree of freedom - a fragment of the product of the variable value of the projection of the mass number, which separates the main functions as part of the functional structure of any isotope. Thus, the entire periodic numerical array, located in the functional contour of a given matrix, can be represented as an internal functional structure of a fragment of the general mass system. In this case, the order and condition are determined by the principle of the state and content of the given mass system. Here, any mass system will be fully adequate to the state of any composition of the isotope series.

Thus, the condition for such definitions is any state of mass systems. For example, extreme short-lived, isotopes of any nuclear symbol. This is an indicator of the limits of "compression" and "expansion" of the functional structure of a given nucleon. The "compression" limit (thermal phase) of which is determined by the internal state of the functional structure of the mass number represented by the isotope. The "expansion" limit (cold phase) is the external state of the content of the functional structure of the mass number of this isotope.

Began

*The value of the definition of the "golden" section ($\pi/6$) does not correspond to the starting count of the formation of the basic conditions of the organic phase of matter. From the point of view of the fundamental data of physical quantities, the mass of Hydrogen (H^1), in the process of "expansion", reduces its charge to the limit of the functional projection of the proton of a stable mass of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (^{16}O). In this case, the number of the Oxygen nucleon determines the minimum offset relative to unity: [**nykl O = (15.9994 / 16) = 0.9999625**].*

The projections of the functional fragments of this "displacement" correspond to:

fmp 0.49965561 and fmn 0.50030689.

This result is only for stable mass numbers of the known table of D. I. Mendeleev. The main difference between the sequence of the order of the process of "expansion" of the structure of Hydrogen (H^1) is the scale of functional limits of the structural projections of "compression" and "expansion". This sequence of stable mirror nuclei is of the following form (Table 1.).

Table 1.

N	z	el	m/n	n	m
61	8	O	16	1	15.9994
62	7	N	14	2	14.0067
63	2	He	4	3	4.0026
64	6	C	12	4	12.011
65	16	S	32	5	32.06
66	20	Ca	40	6	40.08
67	19	K	38	10	0
68	14	Si	28	7	28.0855
69	30	Zn	60	22	0
70	10	Ne	20	8	20.179
71	32	Ge	65	31	0
72	29	Cu	59	24	0
73	31	Ga	63	28	0
74	28	Ni	57	15	0
75	12	Mg	24	9	24.305

Table 1. Fragment of the general table of chemical elements that are in the sequence of periodic limits of the Hydrogen expansion process. Here: **N** is the serial number of the period of the process of expanding the functional structure of Hydrogen. **z** - Charge number. **el** - Chemical element. **m/n** - Mass number of a chemical element. **n** - The serial number of the composition of stable masses of chemical elements in the mathematical cyclic table of all isotopes. **m** - The physical mass of the chemical element.

The main content of this topic is the definition of the conditions and causes of the occurrence of the living phase of matter is the functional structure of the variable values of stable and unstable nuclei of chemical elements. These conditions correspond to ... (**Table 2.**).

Table 2.

N	z	el	m/n	n	m
1	1	H	1	0	0
2	1	H	2	0	0
3	1	H	3	0	0
4	2	He	3	3	0
5	6	C	9	4	0
6	5	B	8	19	0
7	8	O	13	1	0
8	6	C	10	4	0
9	12	Mg	20	9	0
10	7	N	12	2	0
11	10	Ne	17	8	0
12	8	O	14	1	0
13	4	Be	7	29	0
14	12	Mg	21	9	0
15	14	Si	25	7	0
16	16	S	29	5	0
17	10	Ne	18	8	0
18	11	Na	20	14	0
19	18	Ar	33	27	0
20	6	C	11	4	0
21	13	Al	24	12	0
22	20	Ca	37	6	0
23	7	N	13	2	0
24	14	Si	26	7	0
25	39	Y	73	33	0
26	8	O	15	1	0
27	16	S	30	5	0
28	9	F	17	16	0
29	22	Ti	41	21	0
30	21	Sc	40	17	0

Continuation of **Table 2.**

N	z	el	m/n	n	m
31	20	Ca	38	6	0
32	17	Cl	32	13	0
33	11	Na	21	14	0
34	10	Ne	19	8	0
35	13	Al	25	12	0
36	15	P	28	11	0
37	14	Si	27	7	0
38	12	Mg	23	9	0
39	16	S	31	5	0
40	18	Ar	35	27	0
41	21	Sc	41	17	0
42	19	K	37	10	0
43	20	Ca	39	6	0
44	5	B	10	19	0
45	17	Cl	33	13	0
46	3	Li	6	44	0
47	29	Cu	58	24	0
48	28	Ni	56	15	0
49	22	Ti	43	21	0
50	26	Fe	52	18	0
51	15	P	29	11	0
52	18	Ar	36	27	0
53	23	V	46	26	0
54	27	Co	54	23	0
55	25	Mn	50	25	0
56	21	Sc	42	17	0
57	13	Al	26	12	0
58	11	Na	22	14	0
59	24	Cr	48	20	0
60	9	F	18	16	0

Here, the sequence order of (Table 2.) is determined by the number of proton projection fragment. As can be seen, this is not a linear dependence of the order of composition of chemical symbols. For example, the isotopes of Oxygen (O^{13} , O^{14} , O^{15}) are in seventh, twelfth and twenty-sixth places (7, 12, 26).

The correction relative to the functional fragment of the proton projection - the limit of the “compression” process under the conditions of the “linear” order sequence is determined by (Tab. 3.)

Table 3.

N	z	el	m/n	n	fmp	fmn	st/sv
1	2	He	3	4	0.666360472	0.334568695	0.331791777
2	6	C	9	3	0.666360472	0.334289528	0.332070943
3	5	B	8	19	0.624677078	0.358141104	0.266535974
4	8	O	13	1	0.615058513	0.384903987	0.230154526
5	6	C	10	4	0.599669340	0.401259827	0.198409513
6	12	Mg	20	9	0.599669340	0.413330660	0.186338680
7	10	Ne	17	8	0.587901588	0.421248412	0.166653176
8	7	N	12	2	0.582998471	0.417480100	0.165518371
9	4	Be	7	29	0.571091176	0.430264380	0.140826796
10	8	O	14	1	0.571091176	0.428871324	0.142219852
11	12	Mg	21	9	0.571091176	0.441908824	0.129182352
12	14	Si	25	7	0.559660541	0.443410888	0.116249653
13	10	Ne	18	8	0.555215391	0.453934609	0.101280782
14	16	S	29	5	0.551383409	0.450616591	0.100766818
15	11	Na	20	14	0.549659030	0.449897492	0.099761538
16	6	C	11	4	0.545112980	0.455816187	0.089296793
17	18	Ar	33	27	0.545112980	0.453587020	0.091525960
18	13	Al	24	12	0.541324648	0.457990167	0.083334481
19	20	Ca	37	6	0.540198395	0.461801605	0.078396790
20	7	N	13	2	0.538119168	0.462359403	0.075759765
21	14	Si	26	7	0.538119168	0.464952261	0.073166907
22	22	Ti	41	21	0.536242802	0.461673865	0.074568937
23	15	P	28	11	0.535371635	0.463783204	0.071588431
24	8	O	15	1	0.532990458	0.466972042	0.066018416
25	16	S	30	5	0.532990458	0.469009542	0.063980916
26	17	Cl	32	13	0.530906940	0.482035917	0.048871023
27	9	F	17	16	0.529068552	0.470847237	0.058221315
28	10	Ne	19	8	0.525972341	0.483177659	0.042794682
29	20	Ca	38	6	0.525972341	0.476027659	0.049944682
30	21	Sc	40	17	0.524656459	0.474365763	0.050290696
31	11	Na	21	14	0.523465903	0.476090619	0.047375284

Table 3. Principal sequence of isotopes of chemical symbols with respect to the function of the proton fragment. In **table 3**, paired values of equal functional projections of protons of commensurate chemical symbols are highlighted:

fmp ${}_6\text{C}^9 = \text{fmp}_2\text{He}^3$; *fmp* ${}_6\text{C}^{10} = \text{fmp}_{12}\text{Mg}^{20}$; *fmp* ${}_4\text{Be}^7 = \text{fmp}_8\text{O}^{14}$; *fmp* ${}_6\text{C}^{11} = \text{fmp}_{18}\text{Ar}^{33}$; *fmp* ${}_8\text{O}^{15} = \text{fmp}_{16}\text{S}^{30}$; *fmp* ${}_{10}\text{Ne}^{19} = \text{fmp}_{20}\text{Ca}^{38}$

This is what concerns the "warm" phase of the state of periodic development of binary functional projections $((\mathbf{A}+\mathbf{B})/\mathbf{A})^{-1}$. Why "warm"? Due to the advantage of quantitative characterization of the proton function. The total number of all known isotopes with a minor correction is **1458**. This number corresponds to the limiting ratio of the fundamental static physical and genetic quantities of the proton and neutron:

$$\bullet 1458^{-1} \rightarrow \exp^2 \rightarrow 1.001372683 \times \text{mp}(1.00727647) = \text{mn}(1.008659142)$$

The same data is supplemented with the order of natural numbers: **123456789**. Where is the number of natural numbers in the volume: $9^3 = 729 \rightarrow 2(9^3) \rightarrow 1458$.

These are the same binary cyclic projections that form the central meaning of the "displacement" of functional fragments in the region of the space unit \mathbb{E} . In particular, the values of fragments of functional projections (${}_2\text{He}^3$) and (${}_6\text{C}^9$) are approaching the reference functional values. These functional structures provide for potential equal values of neutron composition fragments and degrees of freedom. In this case, the functional division of these values is determined by the structure of the amount of composition of the neutron fragment and the specific content of the numerical event in the form of degrees of freedom. This important number contains basic information about the process of phase exchanges between fragments of the main limits of the proton and neutron functions. In turn, the process of exchanging phase limits forms a variable functional structure, as a result of which the process of reorientation (\times) of the main values of this structure takes place. Thus, it is the period of the result of the reorientation process (\times) that establishes the formation, as a result of division, of two new formations, equal in value, but different in orientation, functional limits. These are vectors of polar signs of the main functions of the "compression" and "expansion" processes. The main information of the content of polar signs (+/-) is determined by the period of reorientation.

The sum of numerical events (+/-), before the reorientation period and the reorientation period, is equal to the main number of the event - the interval between periods of the functional structure of this reorientation process.

The difference of numerical events (+/-), before the period of reorientation and the period of reorientation, is equal to the number of the base of the nucleon - the number of "shift" of the ratio of functional projections in the number of the nucleon.

The determination of the real numbers of protons and neutrons in each isotope of a chemical element made it possible to obtain various variants of the processes of reorientation of functional limits in the compositions of numerical complexes. In this case, the quantitative characteristic and mass value of the organic structure determine the intermediate functional relationships between the genetic cycles of the first protein formations.

For this, a basic periodic sequence of the conditional number of opposite orders of natural numbers was compiled: **123456789....1458** ↔ **987654321....1458**. The conditions for the functional connection of numerical periods occur according to the principle of separation of "paired" functional projections **Table 4**.

Table 4.

N↓	N↑	fmp	fmn	st/sv	n/s
1	1458	0.000685401	0.999314599	-0.998629198	0.000685401
2	1457	0.001370802	0.998629198	-0.997258396	0.000685401
3	1456	0.002056203	0.997943797	-0.995887594	0.000685401
4	1455	0.002741604	0.997258396	-0.994516792	0.000685401
5	1454	0.003427005	0.996572995	-0.99314599	0.000685401
6	1453	0.004112406	0.995887594	-0.991775188	0.000685401
7	1452	0.004797807	0.995202193	-0.990404387	0.000685401
8	1451	0.005483208	0.994516792	-0.989033585	0.000685401

Continuation of **Table 4**.

N↓	N↑	fmp	fmn	st/sv	n/s
1447	12	0.991775188	0.008224812	0.983550377	0.000685401
1448	11	0.992460589	0.007539411	0.984921179	0.000685401
1449	10	0.99314599	0.00685401	0.986291981	0.000685401
1450	9	0.993831391	0.006168609	0.987662783	0.000685401
1451	8	0.994516792	0.005483208	0.989033585	0.000685401
1452	7	0.995202193	0.004797807	0.990404387	0.000685401
1453	6	0.995887594	0.004112406	0.991775188	0.000685401
1454	5	0.996572995	0.003427005	0.99314599	0.000685401
1455	4	0.997258396	0.002741604	0.994516792	0.000685401
1456	3	0.997943797	0.002056203	0.995887594	0.000685401
1457	2	0.998629198	0.001370802	0.997258396	0.000685401
1458	1	0.999314599	0.000685401	0.998629198	0.000685401

Table 4., and continuation of table 4. Are the limits of the values of the functions of the proton and neutron fragments in the periodic system of mass structures. Here, (**n/s**) is the event number of the sum of the functional fragments of the proton and neutron: **fmp + fmn = n/s**.

Table 5.

N↓	N↑	fmp	fmn	st/sv	n/s
720	739	0.493488691	0.506511309	-0.013022618	0.000685401
721	738	0.494174092	0.505825908	-0.011651816	0.000685401
722	737	0.494859493	0.505140507	-0.010281014	0.000685401
723	736	0.495544894	0.504455106	-0.008910212	0.000685401
724	735	0.496230295	0.503769705	-0.007539411	0.000685401
725	734	0.496915696	0.503084304	-0.006168609	0.000685401
726	733	0.497601097	0.502398903	-0.004797807	0.000685401
727	732	0.498286498	0.501713502	-0.003427005	0.000685401
728	731	0.498971899	0.501028101	-0.002056203	0.000685401

Table 5. The result of the reorientation of this functional mass system.

729	730	0.4996573	0.5003427	-0.000685401	0.000685401
730	729	0.5003427	0.4996573	0.000685401	0.000685401
731	728	0.501028101	0.498971899	0.002056203	0.000685401
732	727	0.501713502	0.498286498	0.003427005	0.000685401
733	726	0.502398903	0.497601097	0.004797807	0.000685401
734	725	0.503084304	0.496915696	0.006168609	0.000685401
735	724	0.503769705	0.496230295	0.007539411	0.000685401
736	723	0.504455106	0.495544894	0.008910212	0.000685401
737	722	0.505140507	0.494859493	0.010281014	0.000685401
738	721	0.505825908	0.494174092	0.011651816	0.000685401
739	720	0.506511309	0.493488691	0.013022618	0.000685401

Table 5. Here, periodic projections of fragments of the main functions of protons and neutrons are in ideal conditions of chiral values of the polar content of numerical events. This is the condition for the merging of the external and internal states of the organic phase of matter, when the process of functional "expansion" corresponds to the process of functional "compression".

To determine the organic values of phase transitions, the main functions of the periodic limits of protons and neutrons in the composition of mirror nuclei, a comparative table is proposed (**Table 6.**).

The result of the contents of (**Table 6.**) defines the conditions for the values of the numerical events of the degree of freedom (**st/sv**). To determine the communication periods of the limits of these values, one should use the action of "expansion" and "compression" of each functional fragment relative to the established degree of freedom (**st/sv**): [**fmp / (st/sv)**] and [**fmn / (st/sv)**].

For example, "extension": $fmp_8O^{16} / (st/sv) \rightarrow 0.499655610 / 0.00065128 = 767.190164$

• $fmn_8O^{16} / (st/sv) \rightarrow 0.500306890 / 0.00065128 = 768.190164$

For example, "compression":

• $fmp_8O^{16} \times (st/sv) \rightarrow 0.499655610 \times 0.00065128 = 0.000325416$

• $fmn_8O^{16} \times (st/sv) \rightarrow 0.500306890 \times 0.00065128 = 0.00032584$

Table 6.

N	z	el	m/n	n	m	fmp	fmn	st/sv
1	5	B	10	19		0.499655610	0.483162572	0.016493038
2	3	Li	6	44		0.499655610	0.491630104	0.008025506
3	26	Fe	52	18		0.499655610	0.497612247	0.002043363
4	22	Ti	44	21		0.499655610	0.498261057	0.001394553
5	18	Ar	36	27		0.499655610	0.499044390	0.000611220
6	23	V	46	26		0.499655610	0.499211840	0.000443770
7	27	Co	54	23		0.499655610	0.499212187	0.000443423
8	25	Mn	50	25		0.499655610	0.499217117	0.000438493
9	21	Sc	42	17		0.499655610	0.499366612	0.000288998
10	15	P	30	11		0.499655610	0.499499229	0.000156381
11	13	Al	26	12		0.499655610	0.499659205	-0.000003595
12	11	Na	22	14		0.499655610	0.499900912	-0.000245302
13	9	F	18	16		0.499655610	0.500260179	-0.000604569
14	24	Cr	48	20		0.499655610	0.500267467	-0.000611857
15	8	O	16	1	15.9994	0.499655610	0.500306890	-0.000651280
16	7	N	14	2	14.0067	0.499655610	0.500822961	-0.001167351
17	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.499655610	0.500994390	-0.001338780
18	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.499655610	0.501273557	-0.001617947
19	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499655610	0.502344390	-0.002688780
20	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499655610	0.502344390	-0.002688780
21	19	K	38	10		0.499655610	0.502959775	-0.003304165
22	14	Si	28	7	28.0855	0.499655610	0.503415819	-0.003760209
23	29	Cu	58	24		0.499655610	0.509011057	-0.009355447
24	10	Ne	20	8	20.179	0.499655610	0.509494390	-0.009838780
25	28	Ni	56	15		0.499655610	0.512585769	-0.012930159
26	17	Cl	34	13		0.499655610	0.513287247	-0.013631637
27	12	Mg	24	9	24.305	0.499655610	0.513344390	-0.013688780
28	30	Zn	60	22		0.499655610	0.521750640	-0.022095030

It can be seen here that the reorientation (✕) of the limits is between the tenth and eleventh periods of the mirror nuclei of Phosphorus and Aluminum. The organic phase of stable elements begins with the fifteenth period of a given composition, the first of which is Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$).

These comparative results determine the values of the number and the number field of the ratio of the number of numeric events relative to the minus first power. Here, the projections of the periods of content of organic values of numerical events pass into the genetic phase of viral structures. In physics, such values are referred to as quantum definitions. These are not random numbers, when the projections of the functional values of the limits of the "compression" and "expansion" processes encode their connections in the periodic compositions of the mass system of phase states. For example, the number of the event of the limit of the process of "squeezing" the function of the proton projects the content of the quantity: $0.000325416^{-1} = 3072.98965$. The number of the event of the limit of the "compression" process of the neutron function projects the content of the quantity: $0.00032584^{-1} = 3068.992128$.

Further, the ratio of periods of content in the mass system with the limits of the extreme values of the results of "compression" and "expansion" corresponds to the polymer bond of this functional structure:

$$\bullet 3072.98965 / 767.190164 \rightarrow \text{nykl} = (4.005512316 / 4) = 1.001378079 = \text{mn}/\text{mp}$$

$$\bullet 3068.992128 / 768.190164 \rightarrow \text{nykl} = (3.995094277 / 4) = 0.998773569^{-1} \rightarrow \text{mn}' \cdot {}_8\text{O}^{16}(1.00061378)$$

In this example, the number (1.00061378) is equal to the value of the neutron function number (mn') ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$.

In turn, the value of the proton number (mp') ${}_8\text{O}^{16}$ corresponds to one of the two "number fields" contained in the structure of the "mirror" Helium (${}_2\text{He}^4$): $(\sqrt{\text{nykl}})^{-1} = \text{mp}' (0.999311672)$.

Further, the correspondence of these data:

$$(\mathbf{8mp}' + \mathbf{8mn}') \rightarrow 7.994493376 + 8.00491024 = \mathbf{m} \cdot {}_8\text{O}^{16}(15.99940362).$$

Thus, the distribution of the limits of the main functions of the content of fragments, interconnected projections, determines the value of the external and internal structure of phase functional interactions. This is a condition for a single relationship between the internal and external environment of the content of the organic structure of matter.

Each isotopic series of a chemical element is encoded into the functional structure of its nucleon - a unit of charge. Each nucleon is the sum of fragments of the real numbers of the proton and neutron, and is a functional projection of Hydrogen. This is the "calling card" of the functional structure of any chemical symbol. Each isotope has its own specific functional structure of the reorientation process - a mechanism that separates the external and internal content of a particular structure. In the proposed case, this reorientation mechanism provides functional details of the limit of the composition of the periods of the "compression" process, for each structure of nucleons. It is these details that determine the phase periods of the organic and inorganic nature of matter.

Separation of the external and internal contents of the organic matter phase of the first cycle determines the absolute equality of functional projections. This is the state of the "cold" plasma cycle of merging the external and internal content - the essence of the functional unity of matter.

This state corresponds to the coordination of two main categories of absolute space - area and volume, square and cubic form of content. These data are embedded in the structure of the primary volume unit ($\pi/6$), **Table 7**.

Table 7.

	Basis 1	Phase 1	Phase 2	Volume 1
A	0.5	0.125	0.392699082	0.065449847
	Basis 2	Phase 3	Phase 4	Volume 2
B	0.333333333	0.037037037	0.116355283	0.019392547
	Basis 3	Phase 5	Phase 6	Volume 3
C	0.166666666	0.004629630	0.014544410	0.002406800

The static structure of the volume unit ($\pi/6$) of the composition of cycles: A, B, C.

Here: (Basis 1 + Basis 2 + Basis 3) = 1.

(Phase 1 + Phase 3 + Phase 5) = Basis 3 (0.166666666⁻¹ = 6).

(Phase 2 + Phase 4 + Phase 6) = ($\pi/6$) = 0.523598775.

(Volume 1 + Volume 2 + Volume 3) = pH' (0.087249194⁻¹ = 11.46142393).

The table is compiled according to the classical volume formula:

($\pi(n^{-1})^3$)/6 → Basis = n⁻¹: → Phase = (Basis³ x π)/ 6 = Volume.

A comparative feature of **Table 7**, cycle (C) - the value of the numerical events **Phase 6(0.014544410)** and **Volume 3(0.002406800)** is associated with the content of two numerical events of the functional structure of one proton. This structure determines the interaction of the transition of two dimensions - volumetric and linear expressions of the phase contents of the limits of a given cycle:

$$\cdot \sqrt{\exp(\text{Phase } 6)} = 1.007298712 \text{ and } (\exp(\text{Volume } 3))^3 = 1.007298712 (!)$$

This connection of spatial forms corresponds to the sixth degree: $\sqrt[6]{(\text{mp}^2)} \rightarrow 3\sqrt{\text{mp}}$.

This interaction, defined by the "degree of movement", refers to the expression of the opposite limits of the organic phase of matter. In this case, the value of any number is determined by the functional structure of its period, that is, the quantitative characteristic of numerical events. A characteristic feature of this definition is the formation of a functional structure of a periodic charge, when the fractional values of the displacement position, which is part of the nucleon, refer to simple integer natural numbers. For example, the composition of eight neutrons:

(mn_8O^{16} ; ${}_7\text{N}^{14}$; ${}_2\text{He}^4$; ${}_6\text{C}^{12}$; ${}_{16}\text{S}^{32}$; ${}_{20}\text{Ca}^{40}$; ${}_{14}\text{Si}^{28}$; ${}_{10}\text{Ne}^{20}$), mirror nuclei encodes the functional structure of the Oxygen charge projection **Table 8**.

Table 8.

N	z	el	n/m	m	fmp	fmn	fr/mp	m/z	nykl/z	(nykl/z) ⁻¹
1	8	O	16	15.9994	0.499655610	0.500306890	0.124423599	8.037060587	1.004632573	0.995388788
2	7	N	14	14.0067	0.499655610	0.500822961	0.124551943	8.02877883	1.003597354	0.996415541
3	6	C	12	12.011	0.499655610	0.501273557	0.124664003	8.021561742	1.002695218	0.997312027
4	2	He	4	4.0026	0.499655610	0.500994390	0.124594576	8.026031563	1.003253945	0.996756608
5	16	S	32	32.06	0.499655610	0.502344390	0.124930314	8.004462411	1.000557801	0.99944251
6	20	Ca	40	40.08	0.499655610	0.502344390	0.124930314	8.004462411	1.000557801	0.99944251
7	14	Si	28	28.0855	0.499655610	0.503415819	0.125196772	7.987426368	0.998428296	1.001574178
8	10	Ne	20	20.179	0.499655610	0.509494390	0.12670848	7.892131623	0.986516453	1.013667838
						sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
						4.020996787	1.000000000	64.001915535	8.000239442	8.000000000

Table 8. Here: **fr/mp** is a functional fragment of the charge of the composition of eight periodic elements. **m/z** is the mass projection of the charge fragment.

nykl/z is the number of charge nucleon.

(**nykl/z**)⁻¹ – functional projection of the numerical field of the charge fragment nucleon. **sum** are the sums of the compositions of the functional structure of neutrons.

As can be seen from the data in **Table 8**, functional fragments of a given composition of neutrons form the structure of a unit: $\text{sum}(8\text{fr}/\text{mp} = 1)$. This is the condition of the function of the reduced proton in the given composition. The value of the functions of reduced neutrons, in this composition, will correspond to the action: $(1 - \text{fr}/\text{mp}) = \text{fr}/\text{mn}$. The sum of these eight fragments will be equal to seven. Any content of this composition of eight periods will correspond to the value of one eighth of the unit. The composition of nine periods is one ninth of a unit. The composition of a hundred periods is one hundredth, and so on. This is typical for determining any sequence of ordinal compositions. These numbers decipher the functional structures of any genetic and quantum periods. In this case, the order of the composition of eight periods, the sum of the numbers of freedom - the difference in functional limits will be equal to six.

Thanks to these data, it is possible to decipher the countdown of the first cyclic functional interactions, the main functions of the organic structure. The process of formation of the genetic environment, which is in the phase of the process of reorientation, when there is a functional separation of the projections of the external and internal content of the limits of this formation. This state, the state of productive organic plasma, is within the limits of functional projections in the form of a variable phase of exchange, which determines the future periodic structure of the genome. The process of formation of periodic limits - restrictions that are in the state of the phase of exchange, occurs due to an increase in the "pose" of mixing genetic, quantum periods that do not correspond to the equality of functional projections. In this case, for example, the same functional structure of one eighth of a unit of one composition will not be equal to one eighth of a unit of another composition ($1 \neq 1$). Compare for yourself, **Table 8 (a)**.

Table 8 (a).

N	z	el	n/m	m	fmp	fmn	fr/mp	m/z	nykl/z	(nykl/z)
1	15	P	30	11	0.499655610	0.499499229	0.124504481	8.031839459	1.003979932	0.996035845
2	17	Cl	34	13	0.499655610	0.513287247	0.127941263	7.816086685	0.977010836	1.023530102
3	18	Ar	36	27	0.499655610	0.499044390	0.124391108	8.039159837	1.00489498	0.995128864
4	19	K	38	10	0.499655610	0.502959775	0.125367051	7.976577485	0.997072186	1.002936412
5	21	Sc	42	17	0.499655610	0.499366612	0.124471425	8.033972478	1.00424656	0.995771397
6	22	Ti	44	21	0.499655610	0.498261057	0.124195856	8.051798471	1.006474809	0.993566845
7	23	V	46	26	0.499655610	0.499211840	0.124432846	8.036463272	1.004557909	0.995462771
8	24	Cr	48	20	0.499655610	0.500267467	0.124695971	8.019505328	1.002438166	0.997567764
						sum	sum	sum	sum	sum
						4.011897617	1.000000000	64.005403014	8.000675377	8.000000000

These are very subtle and sensitive structures. This information is contained in the mass system of all isotopes in **tables 4, 5**. This concentration of the "compression" and "expansion" limits, which is in the periods of the reorientation process (**⌘**), determines the comparative data of the functional structures presented in **tables 8 and 8(a)**.

In this case, **tables 8 and 8(a)** proton fragment (**fr/mp**) is determined by the extension function, for example: **sum(4.011897617)/fnn(0.499499229)**. This function determines the place of this value in the total mass system relative to the number of the composition quantity event, for example: **fnn(0.499499229)/(1458)⁻¹ → 728.2698759**.

These are close periods to the result of reorientation of functional limits: (**728 - 731**) of **Table 5**. Further, the content information of the proton fragment: (**fr/mp**) → **0.124504481**, will correspond to the periods of the limits: (**181 - 1268**).

A fragment of the neutron function in this period will correspond to the value: **fnn(0.875086266)**.

Degree of freedom: **st/sv(0.750172533)**.

These intermediate informational data are presented to determine the isotope formations in the structural plasma, when the comparative data of the extreme periodic orders of the "compression" and "expansion" processes form the phase structures of functional matter. For the genetic conditions of the periods of the mass system, a cyclic functional connection of the projections of the main limits is formed. That is, each value is encoded by a multiple content. It is this feature that forms the proper functional structure of the phase state of the period of the main limits.

For example: degree of freedom number: **st/sv(0.750172533)**, limits periods: (**181 - 1268**), corresponds to the transformed proton function within periods (**1087 - 362**). The number of the degree of freedom, in this case, corresponds to: **st/sv(0.500345066)**, and the number of the neutron function: **fnn(0.249827467)**. In this case, the neutron function number becomes twice the proton function number. This is due to the multiplicity of the "compression" period, that is, the number: (**181 x 2**) = **362**.

In turn, the limit of the "expansion" of these values will be: (**1268 - 181**) = **1087**, that is, these limits: (**1087 - 362**).

It should be said about even and odd periodic values of the order of the composition of the functional limits. In this case, the variable function of the event number is encoded only in the even order of the periodic sequence. Only in even periods, the number of events acquires a consistent value of the neutron function.

For example, $\frac{1}{2}$ part of the fragment of the neutron function: **fmn(0.995169082)** of the odd period of limits: (7 - **1442**), is the function of the neutron: **fmn(0.497584541)** of the even period of the limits: (**728** - **721**).

For more recent genetic structures, these data refer to the features of t-cells. Thus, the limits of the periods: (**728** - **721**), are beyond the periods of reorientation. Whereas, the limits of the periods: (**721** - **728**), are before the periods of reorientation. Here, the number (**0.497584541**) of the neutron function becomes the number of the proton function. Separation of even and odd orders of periodic functional limits leads the variable values with respect to the degree of freedom (highlighted values of **Table 4.**). In this case, the expression of even and odd functional projections doubles due to the values of odd periods.

This array is focused on the functional transformation of the limits that form the structure of phase distributions. In other words, there is a transformation of a part of the organic plasma into the content medium of another part of the organic plasma due to the substance located between the limits of functional projections. In late genetic structures, this transformation forms stem cells, receptor and impulse communication systems of biological content limits. For such definitions of model expressions of periodic projections that form the functional structures of the compositions of genetic limiting values, the "transfer" of information on the separation and merging of the starting and final contents of phase exchanges, the structure of the limits of the reduced genome unit is used. In this case, the evolutionary process of the genetic matrix is modulated. In a certain sense, this matrix is represented by a given complex of a model containing a structure consisting of units, the number of which corresponds to the functional composition of a certain genetic period. In other words, all degrading functional projections of the "expansion" limit period tend to the "compression" limit period, that is, to unity. Thus, the processes of development and degradation are in a cyclical state of "association" and "separation" of the structural compositions of the functional complexes of the unit. For example, each of the three bases of the structure of the volume unit of **table 7**, in the process of "degradation" of the degree of movement of the square root, acquires the final value of three units within thirty to thirty-four periods as part of nine-digit numbers.

The general coding of the limits of the degree of movement of the numerical events of the processes of "compression" and "expansion" are presented in **table 9**.

Table 9.

<i>The functional structure of each degree of motion in the processes compression and expansion</i>											
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	compres	expans.
9	0.111	0.0123	0.0013	0.00015	1.69E-05	1.88E-06	2.09E-07	2.32E-08	2.5811E-09	1.146E-43	1.08E+41
8	0.125	0.0156	0.0019	0.0002	3.05E-05	3.81E-06	4.77E-07	5.96E-08	7.4505E-09	2.3E-41	6.81E+38
7	0.142	0.0204	0.0029	0.00041	5.95E-05	8.5E-06	1.21E-06	1.73E-07	2.4780E-08	9.35E-39	2.18E+36
6	0.166	0.0277	0.0046	0.00077	0.00012	2.14E-05	3.57E-06	5.95E-07	9.9229E-08	9.62E-36	2.89E+33
5	0.2	0.04	0.008	0.0016	3.2E-04	6.4E-05	1.3E-05	2.6E-06	5.1E-07	3.52E-32	1.14E+30
4	0.25	0.0625	0.01562	0.0039	0.00097	0.000244	6.1E-05	1.53E-05	3.8147E-06	8.08E-28	7.74E+25
3	0.333	0.11111	0.0370	0.01234	0.004115	0.00137	0.00045	0.00015	5.0805E-05	3.38E-22	3.28E+20
2	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625	0.03125	0.01562	0.00781	0.0039	0.0019531	2.84E-14	8.8E+12
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Matrices of numerical structures of these values represent the state of phase formations within the limits of primary mergers of the extreme values of spatial matter, which is in the state of "cold" cycles.

Matrix 1.

n	$\sqrt[2]{n}$	n^2	n-n	s	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
10	3.16227766	100	19	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	9 sum
9	3	81	17	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-7	-27	-35 sum
8	2.82842712	64	15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	6	20	48	75 sum
7	2.64575131	49	13	2	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-5	-14	-28	-42	-90 sum
6	2.44948974	36	11	2	0	0	0	0	1	4	9	14	14	0	42 sum
5	2.23606798	25	9	2	0	0	0	-1	-3	-5	-5	0	14	42	42 sum
4	2	16	7	2	0	0	1	2	2	0	-5	-14	-28	-48	-90 sum
3	1.73205081	9	5	2	0	-1	-1	0	2	5	9	14	20	27	75 sum
2	1.41421356	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-35 sum
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10 sum
	22.4682782	385	100	19	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3
	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum

Matrix 1. Model, the reasons for the content of the structure - the difference in the limits of the degree of the square, consisting of ten periods. Here the limits of the second period form an event horizon series of order of composition: **sum(3210-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8)=-35**. **n-n** → number of periodic transitions of odd values, the sum of which corresponds to the limit number of composition **n²= 100**. As can be seen, the sum of the vertical sums of finite values is three. In this case, the numerical periodic values of this sum are the structure of the number of the sum, that is, three.

Matrix 2.

n	$\sqrt[3]{n}$	n^3	n-n	s	s'	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	sum	
10	2.15443469	1000	271	54	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-4	-5	sum
9	2.08008382	729	217	48	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	-3	1	sum
8	2	512	169	42	6	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-2	6	48	51	sum
7	1.91293118	343	127	36	6	0	0	0	0	1	1	-8	-42	-126	-174	sum
6	1.81712059	216	91	30	6	0	0	0	-1	0	9	34	84	168	294	sum
5	1.70997595	125	61	24	6	0	0	1	-1	-9	-25	-50	-84	-126	294	sum
4	1.58740105	64	37	18	6	0	-1	2	8	16	25	34	42	48	174	sum
3	1.44224957	27	19	12	6	1	-3	-6	-8	-9	-9	-8	-6	-3	-51	sum
2	1.25992105	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	0	sum
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9	sum
	16.9641179	3025	1000	271	54	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	5	
	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	sum	

Matrix 2. Model, the reasons for the content of the structure, the difference in the limits of the degree of the cube, consisting of ten periods. As can be seen, with the same volume, the linear horizontal grid of the matrix composition is reduced. Here the limits of the second period form an event horizon series of order of composition:

$\text{Sum}(876543210-1-2-3-4) = 0$. Thus, before you is a demonstration of the numerical structure of zero - a number that contains tensor values of functional transitions of volumetric and linear projections.

$n-n \rightarrow$ the number of periodic transitions of odd values, the sum of which corresponds to the limit number of the composition $n^3 = 1000$. As you can see, the sum of the vertical sums of the final values is equal to five. In this case, the numerical periodic values of this sum are the structure of the number of the sum, that is, five.

The data of **matrices 1** and **2** represent the subject content of **DNA** barcodes **3'** and **5'**, the very transition of two dimensions - volumetric and linear phase formations of organic bond limits
Table 7.

Returning to the data of **tables 8** and **tables 8(a)** of neutron functional compositions, the content of these structures should be supplemented with respect to the function of the proton.

This is an important definition from the point of view of the regeneration of organic functional projections in the composition of the genome in relation to the limits of the processes of "compression" and "expansion" **Table 10.**

Table 10.

<i>n/s (mn O)</i>	A	<i>n/s (mn O)</i>	B
0.000613592	<i>Ln(O mn)</i>	0.000613592	<i>Ln(O nm)</i>
0.001644569	<i>Ln(N mn)</i>	0.001986805	<i>Ln(He nm)</i>
0.001986805	<i>Ln(He mn)</i>	0.005902098	<i>Ln(K nm)</i>
0.002543876	<i>Ln(C mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(S nm)</i>
0.004677822	<i>Ln(Ca mn)</i>	0.002543876	<i>Ln(C nm)</i>
0.004677822	<i>Ln(S mn)</i>	0.001644569	<i>Ln(N nm)</i>
0.005902098	<i>Ln(K mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(Ca nm)</i>
5.71587E+11	expansion	5.71587E+11	expansion
1.74951E-12	expa.⁻¹	1.74951E-12	expa.⁻¹
6.58683E-19	compres.	6.58683E-19	compres.

Here, $n/s(mnO) \rightarrow$ base is the number of the neutron event, in this case, the first base of Oxygen (sO^{16}), the proposed composition. **A**- is the sequence order of the proposed composition. **B** - is the second, modified order of the sequence of the proposed composition. The difference between the orders (**A**) and (**B**) is the sequence of elements in the structure. Uniting these orders (**A**) and (**B**) will be the circumstance that the first element is Oxygen. This condition will preserve the equality of the values of "compression" and "expansion" for any sequence of compositions of the remaining elements. In this case, a structure regeneration function is encoded.

The following tensors - the first base of the total composition: (**C**), (**D**), (**E**), (**F**), (**G**), can also have different orders of numerical events of the corresponding neutrons. This is the genetic phase - the gel of the composition of numerical events, the functional structure, which is determined by the variable value of the tensor connection of the protein - the contour of the content of each type of composition. In this case, the encoding of the sequence of each order is determined by the corresponding function in the total composition of numerical events. Thus, violation of the protocol of any function leads to a change in the contour - the type of content. These data take into account the natural decay periods of chemical elements and the functional transitions of nuclear structures. Therefore, the content of the tables: **Table 10** and **Table 10(a)**, is an explanatory part of the main text of this topic.

Table 10 (a).

C	<i>n/s (mn C)</i>	D	<i>n/s (mn N)</i>	E	<i>n/s (mn He)</i>	F	<i>n/s (mn K)</i>	G	<i>n/s (mn Ca)</i>
<i>Ln(C mn)</i>	0.002543876	<i>Ln(N mn)</i>	0.001644569	<i>Ln(He mn)</i>	0.001986805	<i>Ln(K mn)</i>	0.005902098	<i>Ln(Camn)</i>	0.004677822
<i>Ln(N mn)</i>	0.001644569	<i>Ln(He mn)</i>	0.001986805	<i>Ln(O mn)</i>	0.000613592	<i>Ln(Ca mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(Omn)</i>	0.000613592
<i>Ln(K mn)</i>	0.005902098	<i>Ln(S mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(Ca mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(He mn)</i>	0.001986805	<i>Ln(CCmn)</i>	0.002543876
<i>Ln(Ca mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(K mn)</i>	0.005902098	<i>Ln(K mn)</i>	0.005902098	<i>Ln(O mn)</i>	0.000613592	<i>Ln(Kmn)</i>	0.005902098
<i>Ln(O mn)</i>	0.000613592	<i>Ln(O mn)</i>	0.000613592	<i>Ln(C mn)</i>	0.002543876	<i>Ln(S mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(Hemn)</i>	0.001986805
<i>Ln(He mn)</i>	0.001986805	<i>Ln(Ca mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(S mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(C mn)</i>	0.002543876	<i>Ln(Smn)</i>	0.004677822
<i>Ln(S mn)</i>	0.004677822	<i>Ln(C mn)</i>	0.002543876	<i>Ln(N mn)</i>	0.001644569	<i>Ln(N mn)</i>	0.001644569	<i>Ln(Nmn)</i>	0.001644569
<i>expansion</i>	9.82461E+12	<i>expansion</i>	4.10608E+12	<i>expansion</i>	5.99286E+12	<i>expansion</i>	5.28855E+13	<i>expansion</i>	3.32209E+13
<i>expa.⁻¹</i>	1.01785E-13	<i>expa.⁻¹</i>	2.43541E-13	<i>expa.⁻¹</i>	1.66865E-13	<i>expa.⁻¹</i>	1.89088E-14	<i>expa.⁻¹</i>	3.01016E-14
<i>compres.</i>	6.58683E-19								

For modulation conditions of tensor charges capable of reproducing adequate projections of the functional structures of the energy phase, the numbers of nucleons containing all isotopes of one chemical element, as well as the compositions of individual stable nuclei, can be used.

Thus, the first any element determines the constant limit of the entire variable composition of the structure of the "expansion" process. In turn, the limit of the process of "compression" of this composition will be constant for any combination of arguments of this functional structure. In this case, the internal content of the functional structure of the "compression" limit and the "expansion" argument is determined by a variable sequence of structural formations. In this sense, containment conditions determine the reason for containment. In other words, the phase exchange between the internal and external content of a functional structure, in the form of a content medium and an organism of the educational environment, is subject to variable orders of the same composition. In this case, all ordinal composition arguments are in cyclic interaction of their functional limits.

For example, the order sequence of the proton function forms the structure of the composition of the "compression" fragments. In turn, the sequence of the order of the neutron function forms the structure of the composition of the "expansion" fragments. These are completely different functional structures in their content. The next order difference is introduced by the sequence of degrees of freedom. For example, **tables 11, 11(a), 11(b)**.

Table11.

"compression"							"expansion"						
Order sequence of proton fragments							Sequence of neutron fragments						
N	z	el	mass	n	st/mass	fmp	N	z	el	mass	n	st/mass	fmp
43	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.499656	43	3	Li	6	44		0.4996556
44	3	Li	6	44		0.499656	44	26	Fe	52	18		0.4996556
45	5	B	10	19		0.499656	45	17	Cl	33	13		0.5148074
46	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.499656	46	22	Ti	44	21		0.4996556
47	7	N	14	2	14.007	0.499656	47	18	Ar	36	27		0.4996556
48	8	O	16	1	15.999	0.499656	48	23	V	46	26		0.4996556
49	9	F	18	16		0.499656	49	27	Co	54	23		0.4996556
50	10	Ne	20	8	20.179	0.499656	50	25	Mn	50	25		0.4996556
51	11	Na	22	14		0.499656	51	21	Sc	42	17		0.4996556
52	12	Mg	24	9	24.305	0.499656	52	15	P	30	11	30.97376	0.4996556
53	13	Al	26	12		0.499656	53	13	Al	26	12		0.4996556
54	14	Si	28	7	28.086	0.499656	54	11	Na	22	14		0.4996556
55	15	P	30	11	30.974	0.499656	55	9	F	18	16		0.4996556
56	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499656	56	24	Cr	48	20		0.4996556
57	17	Cl	34	13		0.499656	57	8	O	16	1	15.9994	0.4996556
58	18	Ar	36	27		0.499656	58	7	N	14	2	14.0067	0.4996556
59	19	K	38	10		0.499656	59	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.4996556
60	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499656	60	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.4996556
61	21	Sc	42	17		0.499656	61	34	Se	70	45		0.4853702
62	22	Ti	44	21		0.499656	62	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.4996556
63	23	V	46	26		0.499656	63	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.4996556
64	24	Cr	48	20		0.499656	64	19	K	38	10		0.4996556
65	25	Mn	50	25		0.499656	65	14	Si	28	7	28.0855	0.4996556
66	26	Fe	52	18		0.499656	66	26	Fe	53	18		0.4902218
67	27	Co	54	23		0.499656	67	27	Co	55	23		0.4905648
68	28	Ni	56	15		0.499656	68	34	Se	71	45		0.4785295
69	29	Cu	58	24		0.499656	69	29	Cu	58	24		0.4996556
70	30	Zn	60	22		0.499656	70	25	Mn	51	25		0.4898518

Successive orders of fragments of the function of the proton of the composition of "mirror" nuclei within the same periodic volume 43 - 70. It can be seen how the process of expanding the function of the neutron changes the periodic structure of the content of the volume limit. There was a "capture" of new "not" "mirror" elements: **(61)₃₄Se⁷⁰**, **(66)₂₆Fe⁵³**, **(67)₂₇Co⁵⁵**, **(68)₃₄Se⁷¹**, **(70)₂₅Mn⁵¹**.

Table11 (a).

"compression"							"expansion"						
Order sequence of proton fragments							Sequence of proton fragments						
<i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>
43	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.499656	43	84	Po	217	78		0.386037
44	3	Li	6	44		0.499656	44	95	Am	246	94		0.386228
45	5	B	10	19		0.499656	45	83	Bi	215	86		0.386466
46	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.499656	46	90	Th	233	101		0.386505
47	7	N	14	2	14.0067	0.499656	47	89	Ac	230	92		0.386535
48	8	O	16	1	15.9994	0.499656	48	92	U	238	103	238.03	0.386630
49	9	F	18	16		0.499656	49	78	Pt	201	82		0.386770
50	10	Ne	20	8	20.179	0.499656	50	81	Tl	209	87		0.386770
51	11	Na	22	14		0.499656	51	94	Pu	243	104		0.386770
52	12	Mg	24	9	24.305	0.499656	52	96	Cm	248	100		0.386907
53	13	Al	26	12		0.499656	53	98	Cf	253	95		0.386997
54	14	Si	28	7	28.0855	0.499656	54	53	I	137	53		0.387025
55	15	P	30	11	30.9738	0.499656	55	51	Sb	132	51		0.387061
56	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499656	56	91	Pa	235	89		0.387173
57	17	Cl	34	13		0.499656	57	82	Pb	212	88		0.387233
58	18	Ar	36	27		0.499656	58	82	Pb	211	88		0.387270
59	19	K	38	10		0.499656	59	93	Np	240	91		0.387338
60	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499656	60	55	Cs	142	57		0.387428
61	21	Sc	42	17		0.499656	61	95	Am	245	94		0.387523
62	22	Ti	44	21		0.499656	62	54	Xe	139	59		0.387604
63	23	V	46	26		0.499656	63	90	Th	232	101	232.04	0.387673
64	24	Cr	48	20		0.499656	64	80	Hg	206	84		0.387733
65	25	Mn	50	25		0.499656	65	88	Ra	227	98		0.387733
66	26	Fe	52	18		0.499656	66	83	Bi	214	86		0.387801
67	27	Co	54	23		0.499656	67	97	Bk	250	90		0.387859
68	28	Ni	56	15		0.499656	68	36	Kr	93	46		0.387908
69	29	Cu	58	24		0.499656	69	98	Cf	252	95		0.388022
70	30	Zn	60	22		0.499656	70	92	U	237	103		0.388103

Table11 (b).

"compression"							"expansion"						
Order sequence of proton fragments							The sequence of numbers of events						
<i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>
43	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.499656	43	16	S	31	5		0.515785
44	3	Li	6	44		0.499656	44	29	Cu	60	24		0.482989
45	5	B	10	19		0.499656	45	32	Ge	66	31		0.484504
46	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.499656	46	31	Ga	65	28		0.476579
47	7	N	14	2	14.0067	0.499656	47	20	Ca	39	6		0.512476
48	8	O	16	1	15.9994	0.499656	48	4	Be	7	29		0.571091
49	9	F	18	16		0.499656	49	35	Br	74	35		0.472630
50	10	Ne	20	8	20.179	0.499656	50	8	O	15	1		0.532990
51	11	Na	22	14		0.499656	51	9	F	17	16		0.529069
52	12	Mg	24	9	24.305	0.499656	52	11	Na	20	14		0.549659
53	13	Al	26	12		0.499656	53	13	Al	24	12		0.541325
54	14	Si	28	7	28.0855	0.499656	54	40	Zr	86	34		0.464774
55	15	P	30	11	30.97376	0.499656	55	15	P	28	11		0.535372
56	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499656	56	14	Si	28	7	28.0855	0.499656
57	17	Cl	34	13		0.499656	57	30	Zn	67	22		0.447421
58	18	Ar	36	27		0.499656	58	11	Na	21	14		0.523466
59	19	K	38	10		0.499656	59	10	Ne	21	8		0.475847
60	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499656	60	18	Ar	33	27		0.545113
61	21	Sc	42	17		0.499656	61	19	K	38	10		0.499656
62	22	Ti	44	21		0.499656	62	28	Ni	60	15		0.466324
63	23	V	46	26		0.499656	63	8	O	14	1		0.571091
64	24	Cr	48	20		0.499656	64	21	Sc	40	17		0.524656
65	25	Mn	50	25		0.499656	65	32	Ge	67	31		0.477268
66	26	Fe	52	18		0.499656	66	13	Al	25	12		0.519656
67	27	Co	54	23		0.499656	67	29	Cu	61	24		0.475066
68	28	Ni	56	15		0.499656	68	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499656
69	29	Cu	58	24		0.499656	69	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499656
70	30	Zn	60	22		0.499656	70	31	Ga	66	28		0.469354

The orders of the processes of "compression" and "expansion" within (43 - 70) of the total periodic volume. Here, the discrepancy between periodic structures of a given volume occurs due to the orders of the process of "compression" of the proton function and the process of "expansion" of the function of the number of degrees of freedom.

All previous tables contain the changing functional "density" of the structure of one certain volume of periodic limits. At the same time, the amount of the composition does not change - its content changes.

Here, it should be said about the results of "capture" and "allocation" of structures of fragments of functional projections that are in the process of "compression" and "expansion" **Table 12.**

Table 12.

"compression"							"expansion"							
Ordersequence of proton fragments							Capture of additional fragments							
<i>N</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>	<i>N'</i>	<i>N''</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>el</i>	<i>mass</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>st/mass</i>	<i>fmp</i>
43	2	He	4	3	4.0026	0.4996556	1	1	30	Zn	60	22	-	0.499656
44	3	Li	6	44		0.4996556	2	10	10	Ne	19	8	-	0.525972
45	5	B	10	19		0.4996556	3	11	12	Mg	20	9		0.599669
46	6	C	12	4	12.011	0.4996556	4	12	12	Mg	24	9	24.31	0.499656
47	7	N	14	2	14.007	0.4996556	5	13	17	Cl	34	13		0.499656
48	8	O	16	1	15.999	0.4996556	6	14	28	Ni	56	15		0.499656
49	9	F	18	16		0.4996556	7	19	10	Ne	20	8	20.18	0.499656
50	10	Ne	20	8	20.179	0.4996556	8	21	29	Cu	58	24	-	0.499656
51	11	Na	22	14		0.4996556	9	22	31	Ga	63	28		0.491719
52	12	Mg	24	9	24.305	0.4996556	10	56	14	Si	28	7	28.09	0.499656
53	13	Al	26	12		0.4996556	11	61	19	K	38	10		0.499656
54	14	Si	28	7	28.086	0.4996556	12	68	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.499656
55	15	P	30	11	30.974	0.4996556	13	69	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.499656
56	16	S	32	5	32.06	0.4996556	14	79	6	C	12	4	12.01	0.499656
57	17	Cl	34	13		0.4996556	15	80	2	He	4	3	4.003	0.499656
58	18	Ar	36	27		0.4996556	16	81	7	N	14	2	14.01	0.499656
59	19	K	38	10		0.4996556	17	84	8	O	16	1	16	0.499656
60	20	Ca	40	6	40.08	0.4996556	18	85	24	Cr	48	20		0.499656
61	21	Sc	42	17		0.4996556	19	86	9	F	18	16	-	0.499656
62	22	Ti	44	21		0.4996556	20	87	30	Zn	68	22	-	0.440837
63	23	V	46	26		0.4996556	21	91	29	Cu	62	24		0.467399
64	24	Cr	48	20		0.4996556	22	92	11	Na	22	14	-	0.499656
65	25	Mn	50	25		0.4996556	23	94	31	Ga	67	28		0.462344
66	26	Fe	52	18		0.4996556	24	95	13	Al	26	12	-	0.499656
67	27	Co	54	23		0.4996556	25	97	15	P	30	11	30.97	0.499656
68	28	Ni	56	15		0.4996556	26	98	21	Sc	42	17	-	0.499656
69	29	Cu	58	24		0.4996556	27	100	40	Zr	88	34	-	0.454204
70	30	Zn	60	22		0.4996556	28	101	25	Mn	50	25	-	0.499656

Continuation of **Table 12**.

	29	102	27	Co	54	23	-	0.499656
	30	103	23	V	46	26		0.499656
	31	104	18	Ar	36	27	-	0.499656
	32	105	16	S	33	5	-	0.484504
	33	107	22	Ti	44	21		0.499656
	34	108	32	Ge	69	31		0.463426
	35	109	24	Cr	49	20		0.489452
	36	110	26	Fe	52	18		0.499656
	37	179	3	Li	6	44		0.499656
<i>The result of violation</i>	38	180	47	Ag	105	38		0.447278
<i>of the sequence of composition</i>	39	181	36	Kr	76	46		0.473341
<i>of fragments of protons</i>	40	182	7	N	15	2		0.466324
<i>of mirror nuclei by the order</i>	41	183	31	Ga	70	28	69.72	0.442517
<i>of numerical events.</i>	42	184	15	P	32	11		0.468407
<i>In the column (n")</i>	43	185	51	Sb	113	51		0.450986
<i>there are new serial numbers</i>	44	186	29	Cu	65	24		0.445813
<i>of "scattered" fragments of protons.</i>	45	334	5	B	10	19		0.499656

Table 12. Here is the content of the periodic volume of "compression" **43 - 70**(column **N**), the composition of mirror nuclei and the projection of the "expansion" of the selected composition in the amount of **28** (column **N'**). Column (**N''**) gives the result of a sequence of "expansion" in a combination of different periods in the structure of the same volume.

The data presented in **table 12** demonstrate the principle of the essence of "separation" and "capture" of the limiting periodic orders that are in the structure of the mass system. This function is a projection link between the internal and external content of the mass structure. This is the primary cyclic function, separating and uniting fragments of the main polar processes of "compression" and "expansion". In physical terms, this is the amplitude - the range - the period containing the wave characteristics. The wave, like the structure of functional limits, contains a "transfer" of one structure of the composition of projections to another composition of opposite projections, back and forth, changing the content and structure of the functional limits of the external and internal environment. To physicists, this definition represents cascades of impulse responses—periodic reorientations known as photons and neutrinos.

Here it should be said that the values of the functional limits presented in tables 4 and 5 of this text demonstrate the principle of the periodic relationship of quantum values between the limits of their functional projections. In particular, the ordinal limits of these tables. Here, the number of the event of the number of the order of periods encodes the quantum number of its projection: $1458^{-1} = 0.000685871$, where the phases of the exchange of these values: $[(A+B)/A]^{-1}$ and $[(A+B)/B]^{-1}$, determine the forward and reverse periodic relationship, in as a result of which, the number of the event becomes a photon - a light projection of the informative connection of functional limits.

In this case, the neutrino is only a function - a function of the value "zero", which encodes and accompanies the processes of reorientation of the functional limits of structural projections. In genetics, the primary cyclic function that separates and unites the limits of the fragments of the main polar processes of "compression" and "expansion" is the function of "breathing" - the function of "nutrition" - the function of "orientation" in the environment of the mass system. The impulse system is characterized by "capture" and "reflection" of periodic limits, which, in the process of "projection transfer" to the structures of polar limits, become "unstable", due to the combination of functional projections located in one of the structures of "captures" or "allocations". In this case, an impulse is formed - one of the moments of the "reorientation" conditions and the result of the next value of the functional limits. The "information" of this "command" of the "neutrino" of the limits of fragments of functional projections, known as the receptor signal of the state of the "brain phase" of interactions between the internal and external organic environment.

On the topic of this material - the causes and conditions of evolutionary cycles, this content provides a general idea of a specific state of the transition period of one of the cycle of functional limits of the primary volume of the spatial contour of matter. In this case, the principle of separation of the limits of functional projections of fundamental quantities, proton and neutron, is proposed as functions of the processes of "compression" and "expansion" that are in the variable phase of the states of the periods of their projections.

This is the condition of constant "instability" of the phase limits of the internal and external content of the contour of the volume of the space of matter.

The reason for this instability is that the process of maximum "convergence" of the limits of fragments of functional projections - the process of "compression", increases the contour of the limit of the process of "expansion", the subsequent evolutionary cycle as the next process of "compression". In this definition, the limits of the organic phase of the primary volume divide and separate the functional limits of their projections, forming the limits of the binary functional structures of each evolutionary cycle. For example, the functional limits of Hydrogen (H^3) - the double structure of the neutron function, determine the double projection of the proton function. In this case, the "instability" of the "expansion" limit of two neutrons forms the "compression" limit of two protons of the Helium (${}^2He^3$) functional structure. The peculiarity of the limits of the basic functions of the unit contour structure is determined by the real converted numbers of protons and neutrons in the mass number system. The main characteristic of the functional transitions of the limiting values of nuclear structures is the isotopic composition of each number of nucleons - unit charge.

Comparative data of "instability - discrepancies" of the bases of the limits of the degree of movement of the functions of "compression" and "expansion" of the composition of natural numbers in tables **13** and **13(a)**.

Table 13.

<i>The degree of movement of each period as part of the overall of the functional structure (compression)</i>									
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9
9	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000116
8	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.99999994
7	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000008
6	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000022
5	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.999999945
4	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.999999957
3	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000061
2	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000061
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 13. Subject to the contents of **table 9**, the maximum "compression" limit of the negative degree of movement (**-9**) is equal to the value (**5.000000116**) - the number of the degree of "fusion" of the bases of the "compression" limit - the sum of negative degrees (**1.146E-43**) periodic series of natural numbers.

Table 13(a).

<i>The degree of movement of each period in the compositions of structures of general functional relations (expansion)</i>									
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9
9	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777948
8	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777799
7	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777663
6	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777803
5	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777876
4	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777827
3	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777788
2	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777723
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 13(a). Subject to the content of **Table 9**, the maximum "expansion" limit of the negative degree of motion (-9) is equal to the value (-4.77777948) - the number of the "fusion" degree of the bases of the "expansion" limit - the sum of negative degrees (1.08E + 41) of the periodic series of natural numbers. As you can see, the maximum limits of opposite values form the minimum degree of "fusion" of their functional projections.

To demonstrate the encodings of functional limits in structures of the same numerical values, when (n ≠ n), as an example, **Matrix 3** follows.

Matrix 3.

										<i>Expansion</i>	<i>compression</i>		
1	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-362880	-2.75573E-06	(compr.)	(Expans/compr.)
2	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	280	0.01428571	70	4
3	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-40	-0.1	-10	4
4	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	320	0.0125	80	4
5	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-160	-0.1	-10	16
6	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-108	-0.08333333	-12	9
7	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	945	0.00952381	105	9
8	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	3024	0.01190476	84	36
9	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-9072	-0.00099206	-1008	9

Matrix 3. This "absurdity" of symbolic meanings is presented to exclude the concept of "uncertainty" and "chaotic", including the "chaos" of the interaction of the structural contents of natural numbers. The same natural number, which is in different functional periods, has a different structure of its content - the function of definition. In this case, we are talking about the comparative values of the interaction of the extreme limits of scale and periodic communication, and the content of the numerical composition of functional structures formed as a result of the degree of movement. For the convenience of perceiving the content of the result of the "cold" matrix, the sample values are highlighted with an appropriate marker.

As can be seen from the conditions of reorientation, the interaction of opposite periods form the positive and negative structure of their content. These values fall into the conditions of the relationship of functional limits, that is, into the periodic composition of the structure of the event number - the degree of quantity projection. To begin with, it is necessary to explain the role of the negative degree of movement - the content and transfer of large-scale projections in the conditions of the formation of functional fragments of genetic complexes. The principle of interaction between the number and the "field" - the projection of this number determines the phases of "consciousness" of the "ability" of the orientation of the periodic materialization of numerical values. In other words, the number and the "dream" of the number, its field - the projections of the number determine the unity of matter. In this case, this is due to the fact that, for example, the action of "expansion" - the relationship of the number and its "field", in the projection of the minus first degree, "materializes" this unity as a number to the power of the square: $n^2 = (n/n^{-1})$. Subsequently, this action is directly related to the "unity" of the functional structures of RNA and DNA. The basis of this principle was stated at the beginning of this text **table 7**, the conditions for the transition phase - volume. Here, the "extension" of the unity of even phases and odd phases forms the sixth degree. Under the conditions of other values of the negative degree of a series of natural numbers, the result of the "merging" of the projections of the number and the field will correspond to - the number of the degree plus one: $(n^{n+1} = n/n^{-n})$.

Perhaps the attentive reader has already noticed that the functional structures represented by the chemical elements contain specific values of the number and field in the unity of the projections of these data.

Perhaps the attentive reader has already noticed that these projections do not correspond to the static value of merging numbers and fields according to one degree. As a rule, in functional structures, the "fusion" of the reduced projections of the number and the field has a "distorted" degree number. This is the reason for the dynamics of expression. The same value of a number or field can have several projections capable of merging. This ability does not correspond to the physical concepts of "short-range forces". In the genetic, organic sense, this definition would lead to the "petrification" of all living matter. But that doesn't happen. Any periodic sequence of structural functional values does not lead even identical projections to merge. They are distinguished by the structural dynamics of their content - quantitative and numerical complexes of these values. As an example, a table of the functional structure of the Oxygen nucleon reorientation process is proposed **Table 14**.

Table 14.

functional structure of the reorientation of the Oxygen nucleon						
	<i>mp</i>	<i>mn</i>	<i>st/sv</i>	<i>nykl</i>	<i>nykl'</i>	<i>n/s</i>
1	0.999311219	1.00061378	0.001302562	0.9999625	1.00130346	
2	0.999348695	1.00057631	0.001227611	0.9999625	1.001228411	3.7476E-05
3	0.999386172	1.00053883	0.001152657	0.9999625	1.001153365	3.7477E-05
4	0.99942365	1.00050135	0.0010777	0.9999625	1.001078321	3.7478E-05
5	0.99946113	1.00046387	0.00100274	0.9999625	1.001003281	3.748E-05
6	0.999498611	1.00042639	0.000927778	0.9999625	1.000928243	3.7481E-05
7	0.999536094	1.00038891	0.000852813	0.9999625	1.000853209	3.7483E-05
8	0.999573578	1.00035142	0.000777845	0.9999625	1.000778177	3.7484E-05
9	0.999611063	1.00031394	0.000702874	0.9999625	1.000703147	3.7485E-05
10	0.99964855	1.00027645	0.0006279	0.9999625	1.000628121	3.7487E-05
11	0.999686038	1.00023896	0.000552924	0.9999625	1.000553097	3.7488E-05
12	0.999723528	1.00020147	0.000477945	0.9999625	1.000478077	3.749E-05
13	0.999761019	1.00016398	0.000402962	0.9999625	1.000403059	3.7491E-05
14	0.999798511	1.00012649	0.000327978	0.9999625	1.000328044	3.7492E-05
15	0.999836005	1.00008899	0.00025299	0.9999625	1.000253031	3.7494E-05
16	0.9998735	1.0000515	0.000177999	0.9999625	1.000178022	3.7495E-05
17	0.999910997	1.000014	0.000103006	0.9999625	1.000103015	3.7497E-05
18	0.999948495	0.9999765	2.80099E-05	0.9999625	1.000028011	3.7498E-05
19	0.999985995	0.99993901	-4.69891E-05	0.9999625	0.99995301	3.7499E-05
20	1.000023495	0.9999015	-0.000121991	0.9999625	0.999878012	3.7501E-05

Table 14. Phase of the reorientation process: $[((A+B)/A)^{-1}]$.

The phase of the interaction of the field - the real number of the proton and the number - the number of the neutron: $mp' = 0.999311219$; $mn' = 1.00061378$. In this case, the degree of interaction does not correspond to the static value: $\ln(mn')/\ln(mp') = -0.89053033$.

The limit period of the reorientation process (**18**) brings the value of the neutron number to the value of the field of this function. The overall result of the degree of "transition" of the final projections of the neutron will correspond to: $[\ln(mn')/0.9999765 = -26.10998142]$.

The overall result of the degree of "transition" of the final projections of the proton will correspond to: $[\ln(mp')/0.999948495 = 13.37735399]$.

The erudition of these data is found in various research sources in the content of computational values. In this case, the contour of the functional structure of the process of reorientation of the Oxygen nucleon represents an early model of future chromosomes. The information of the sequence and "interaction" of the given numbers of nucleons in the column (*nykl'*), provides the result of the formation of projections of the next nucleons.

For example, in the sixth period (*nykl'*), the number: **(1.000928243)** corresponds to the number of the Carbon nucleon (${}_6\text{C}^{12}$). The twelfth period (*nykl'*) contains the value of the nucleon of Nitrogen (${}_7\text{N}^{14}$) **(1.000478077)**.

• **1.000928243 x 12 = m₆C¹² = 12.01113892; 1.000478077 x 14 = m₇N¹⁴ = 14.00669308**

The degree of "transition" of these values relative to the Oxygen nucleon will be, respectively:

• **(-24.74119896) and (-12.7454333).**

The first period, the exchange phases of the process of reorientation of the mirror nucleus of Oxygen (${}_8\text{O}^{16}$), corresponds to two nucleons of the mirror nucleus of Helium (${}_2\text{He}^4$):

4[√(1.00130346)] = 4.002606071.

Principal matrix of the structure of reorientation of the basic composition of natural numbers in periods within (9), units of volume: numbers [11 = (2+3+6)] and the field of this Hydrogen density number, (11⁻¹ = pH¹) → (π/ 6)

①	②	③	④	⑤	⑥	⑦	⑧	⑨	⑩	⑪
1 → 10 → 19 → 28 → 37 → 46 → 55 → 64 → 73 → 81 → 82										
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
9 → 8 → 7 → 6 → 5 → 4 → 3 → 2 → 1 → 9 ⁻¹										↕
✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	✕	Z (+/-)
-9 ← -8 ← -7 ← -6 ← -5 ← -4 ← -3 ← -2 ← -1 ← -9 ⁻¹										↕
↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑	↑
163 ← 154 ← 145 ← 136 ← 127 ← 118 ← 109 ← 100 ← 91 ← 83 ← 0										
①	②	③	④	⑤	⑥	⑦	⑧	⑨	⑩	

Periods of reorientation of the structure of the composition of the number nine values of π:

**(11 + 10)⁻¹ = 0.047619048 → 1 - (π / 6) = 0.476401224 → (0.047619048 - 0.047197551 = 0.000421497) → (0.047619048/0.047197551) = fmn(${}_8\text{O}^{16}$)1.000612932 → exp(0.000421497) = 1.000421586 → [Ln(4√1.000421586)]⁴ = 1.2329287 E·10⁻¹⁶ → ((π²)⁻¹)¹⁶ = 1.2336844 E·10⁻¹⁶
Ln(Ln(Ln(π))) = - 2.001231639 → -2.001231639 / 2 → mn' $({}_8\text{O}^{16})$ - 1.000615819**

The static structure of the reorientation of the order of natural numbers that are part of the functional structure of the unit of primary volume(π/ 6) contains the polar limits of the opposite orders of natural numbers of the reorientation of the number nine.

The main limits of the reorientation result are the periods of the square of this number: ($9^2 = 81$), and the next period is the period (**83**), corresponding to the value of the reorientation period, that is, in this case, this is an odd value of the transition periods: (**81 - 83**). The even, ordinal value of the period is the result of the reorientation process (**✕**), the corresponding content within the periods: (**82 - 83**). Here, unity is the number of the "transition" between periods contains two polar values of the charge structure (**Z(+/-)**) - the polar result of the reorientation process, which determines the "possible perspective" of the corresponding connection.

This is the number of period ten - a period containing the composition of the code of two numbers - one and zero ($1 \leftrightarrow 0$) - zero, the structure of which contains the main information of the variable passing (possible or future) connection of the sequence of the composition of the periods that make up this process of reorientation.

Continuing to develop the meaning of the meaning of the number and the field ($n \leftrightarrow n^{-1}$), one should return to the beginning of this material - to the first stable chemical element containing its nucleon in the meaning of the numerical field. This is Oxygen ($8O^{16}$). The second stable element, formed as a result of the "expansion" of the functional structure of Hydrogen, is Nitrogen ($7N^{14}$) - an element whose nucleon is the value of the number: *nykl* $7N^{14} = 1.000478077$. This act consistently develops the expression of the formation of stable nuclear symbols in the projections of nucleons of numerical values. Phosphorus and Sodium, like Oxygen, have nucleons of the number field value **tables 6, 8 and 8(a)**.

The main emphasis of the manifestation of signs of life falls on the "central" periods of reorientation - the concentration of functional fragments of the projections of the values of the number and the field of the number ($n \leftrightarrow n^{-1}$) - the projections of the "daughter" and "mother" nuclei. The determination of the real numbers of protons and neutrons, their functional properties, made it possible to explain the Mössbauer effect obtained as a result of medical research. In this case, the physical version of elastic resonances is inferior to the genetic nature of the "self-organization" of organic matter **tables 10, 10(a)**. This is a reorientation of the functions of protons and neutrons in the structures of the parent and daughter nuclei.

In the genetic definition, this composition of functional fragments is in the structure of the number of nucleons containing all isotopes (*in percentage terms*) of a given element.

For example, the first phase of Hydrogen expansion (**1.00794**), to the limit:

Ln ($\sqrt{1.00794}$) = 0.003954322) corresponds to the multiplicative composition of the neutron functions of all isotopes of Oxygen:

$$\bullet (\text{fnnO}^{13}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{14}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{15}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{16}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{17}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{18}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{19}) \cdot (\text{fnnO}^{20}) = 0.003948829$$

Here, the presented set of functional fragments of the oxygen neutron, encodes the structure of the neutron of Helium: **fnn ${}_2\text{He}^4 = [\sqrt{\exp(0.003948829)}] = 1.001976365$.**

This information is encoded by any altered order of fragments of the proton and neutron functions, for example, "compression" of the proton composition of oxygen isotopes:

$$\bullet (\text{fmpO}^{13}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{14}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{15}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{16}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{17}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{18}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{19}) \cdot (\text{fmpO}^{20}) = 0.003284825$$

At the same time, the presented set of functional fragments of the number of Oxygen proton events encodes the structure of the Nitrogen neutron: **fnn' ${}_7\text{N}^{14} = [\sqrt{\exp(0.003284825)}] = 1.001643762$.**

The number of proton and neutron functions in the phase definition is the value of the functional structure in the form of the number of the process occurring in the nucleon. This number may be common to several different isotopes. One such process is the total number of proton functions of mirror isotopes: (**0.49965561**). This functional structure demonstrates the claimed feature of keeping all possible functional fragments in one row. To highlight a specific given functional sequence of an individual isotope, the degree of charge number of this isotope should be used.

For example, for the isotope Oxygen (**${}_8\text{O}^{16}$**), the fragment of the proton function will be a number:

$$\bullet 0.49965561^8 = 0.003884777.$$

For the nitrogen isotope (**${}_7\text{N}^{14}$**) this definition will be a fragment of the proton function:

$$\bullet 0.49965561^7 = 0.00777491.$$

In a quantitative ratio, these functional projections make up the quantitative exchange structures - connections:

$$\bullet 0.49965561 / 0.00388477 = 128.6190971^{-1} \rightarrow 0.007774895$$

$$\bullet 0.49965561 / 0.00777491 = 64.26513104^{-1} (!) \rightarrow 0.015560538$$

The physical connection of these proton mass functions corresponds to the relationship:

$$\bullet 2^{1/2} (0.00777491 / 0.00388477) \rightarrow \text{mp} = 1.00727647; \text{mn} = 1.008669331$$

For Carbon, this information will be the fragment number of the proton function:

$$\bullet \mathbf{0.499655616^6 = 0.015560538^{-1} \rightarrow 64.26513017 (!)}$$

$$\bullet \mathbf{0.499655616 / 0.015560538 = 32.11043289}$$

In this case, the conditions of the Carbon function correspond to the value:

$$\bullet \mathbf{\sqrt{\exp(0.015560538)} = 1.007810614}$$

The genetic balance of agreement of numerical values will be a multiple of the number and field of the Oxygen nucleon: $\mathbf{\exp(1.00794 - 1.007810614)^{-1} = (\text{nyklO})^4}$

These examples are necessary to determine all possible functional values of the same number. In genetic structures, these values are separated by hyperfine functional projections. For example, the sum of the functions of protons and neutrons of Nitrogen is the number of the degree of the proton function of Carbon:

$$\bullet \mathbf{[fmp\ N(0.005108608) + fmn\ N(0.010476667)] = 0.015585275 \leftrightarrow 0.499655616 = 0.015560538^{-1}}$$

The sum of the proton and neutron functions of Phosphorus also corresponds to this value:

$$\bullet \mathbf{[fmp\ P(0.006270516) + fmn\ P(0.009302345)] = 0.015572861}$$

thus, the average number, the sum of the functions of protons and neutrons of Nitrogen and the fragment of the proton function of Carbon, corresponds to the sum of the functions of protons and neutrons of Phosphorus:

$$\bullet \mathbf{\frac{1}{2} (0.015585275 + 0.015560538) = 0.01557'_{1644} \leftrightarrow 0.01557'_{2861}}$$

These data are necessary to accurately determine the functional composition of the structure of each isotope in the genome.

For practical analysis, an analysis of the functional structure of Adenine is proposed: $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}_5)$.

In this functional structure five functions of Hydrogen form five pairs of functions of protons and neutrons of Nitrogen and Carbon. In the general functional definition, the structure of Carbon is the ultimate projection of the genetic processes occurring in the structure of Hydrogen. If Oxygen is present in this process, then the final projection will belong to the functional structure of Phosphorus.

Thus, the composition of the Adenine formula characterizes its significance as a function of this protein in the DNA composition.

The choice of the initial function of nitrogen in the structure of Hydrogen, first of all, forms the number of Hydrogen - the nucleon of the mass number of Adenine (135.13).

- $\text{nykl [A]} = 135.13 / 135 = 1.000962963$

This number corresponds to two projections of the Nitrogen nucleon:

- $\sqrt{1.000962963} = \text{nykl N}(1.000481366)$

The sum of the projections of the proton function of Carbon and Nitrogen: $(6\text{mpC} + 7\text{mpN}) = 13$.

These numerical values of the functions are not equal to each other:

- $(\text{f mp C}^{13} = 0.461196127); (\text{f mn C}^{13} = 0.539733040); (\text{f mp N}^{13} = 0.538119168); (\text{f mn N}^{13} = 0.462359403)$

Thus, the protons of Nitrogen and Carbon form a double functional structure, in which the proton of Nitrogen acquires the function of a neutron. These are isobars. Determining the phases of these elements establishes the real numbers of protons and neutrons:

- $(\text{mp C}^{13} = 0.999258275; \text{mn C}^{13}=1.00236136), (\text{mp N}^{13}= 0.999364169; \text{mn N}^{13}= 1.001778707)$

Mass numbers of these elements: $(\text{mC}^{13}= 13.01207917); (\text{mN}^{13} = 13.00622142)$

Total mass: $(5\text{mC}^{13} + 5\text{mN}^{13})= 130.091503$

The mass of Hydrogen installed $(\text{m}^{\text{H}'})$ is: $(135.13 - 130.091503) / 5 = 1.00769941$

For physical definitions and the connection of general constants, this number determines the main content of the functional structure, relative to the static number of Hydrogen:

- $1.00794 - 1.00769941 = \exp(0.00024059)^4 = 1.000962824 = \text{nykl [A]} (!)$

This implies a complex mechanism for the formation of the Hydrogen number (H') . Function fragment conditions: $(\text{f mp} \times \text{f mn})$, Nitrogen (${}_{7}\text{N}^{13}$) is $(1/2)$ part of the proton function of its isotope (${}_{7}\text{N}^{14}$). The four projections of this part provide the basis for the number of a given Hydrogen (H') :

- $(\text{fmpN13} \cdot \text{fmnN13})^4 = 1/2 (\text{fmpN}^{14}) = 1/2 \text{Ln}(1.00769941)$

Then the conditions are: $135.13 \cdot (1/2 \text{Ln}(1.00769941)) = \text{fmp}({}_{14}\text{Si}^{27})$

The proton number of the isotope $({}_{14}\text{Si}^{27})$ corresponds to the value: $2(\text{f mp})$. These data determine the degree of functional projection of the Oxygen nucleon: $(^{1024}\sqrt{2 (\text{fmp}))}^{-1} = \text{nyklO}$. This degree is the number of projections of the two bases of the Nitrogen Nucleon: $(\text{Ln}(\text{nykl}^2\text{N}))^{-1} = 1024$

The cube root of this degree of composition is equal to ten nucleons of static Hydrogen:

$$\bullet \sqrt[3]{1024} = 10H(10.0794) (!)$$

The double projection, the proton function of the silicon isotope ($_{14}\text{Si}^{27}$), contains the mechanism of the phase transition of the projection, given by the reduced number of Hydrogen:

$$\bullet (H' = 1.00769941) \rightarrow (\sqrt{\text{nyklSi}})^5 = H'$$

Thus, the functional structure of the silicon isotope ($_{14}\text{Si}^{27}$) contains projections of the doubled number of nitrogen protons: ($2n(\text{fmpN}^{13}) \rightarrow (7\text{mp} \leftrightarrow 7\text{mp}) = 14$), and adjacent functions of nitrogen and carbon neutrons: ($6\text{fmnC } 13 \leftrightarrow 6\text{fmnN}^{13}$). Here, the late functional structure retains information these values by crystallizing the functional projections of Hydrogen and Nitrogen. The functional structure forming Adenine is distributed by the nucleon of the reduced Hydrogen number (1.00769941), while the structure of the carbon isotope ($_{6}\text{C}^{13}$) is stabilized, due to the pair projections of the Nitrogen nucleon. In this case, the functional structure of the exchange of the nitrogen isotope ($_{7}\text{N}^{13}$) is a projection sequence of counter fragments of the main functions of the proton and neutron in its structure. The main meaning of this sequence is the double projection of the Nitrogen Nucleon during the period of functional reorientation. For a more detailed analysis of the functional structure, a fragment of the phase model $((A + B)/A)^{-1}$, the process of nitrogen reorientation ($_{7}\text{N}^{13}$) is proposed (Table 15.).

Table 15.

	$_{7}\text{N}^{13}$			
	$((A+B)/A)^{-1}$			
Pr	A \rightarrow f mp	B \rightarrow f mn	st/sv	m \rightarrow 13 ⁻¹
1	0.538119168	0.462359403	0.075759764	0.076923077
2	0.537861763	0.462616808	0.075244954	0.076923077
3	0.537604481	0.46287409	0.07473039	0.076923077
4	0.537347322	0.463131249	0.074216073	0.076923077
5	0.537090286	0.463388285	0.073702001	0.076923077
152	0.500612877	0.499865694	0.000747183	0.076923077
153	0.500373413	0.500105158	0.000268255	0.076923077
154	0.500134063	0.500344508	-0.000210444	0.076923077
155	0.499894828	0.500583743	-0.000688915	0.076923077
156	0.499655707	0.500822864	-0.001167156	0.076923077
157	0.499416701	0.50106187	-0.001645169	0.076923077
158	0.499177809	0.501300762	-0.002122953	0.076923077
159	0.498939031	0.50153954	-0.002600508	0.076923077

Table 15, collapsed view. Here, the first five periods are presented for comparison with the periods of reorientation. This process demonstrates the variability of the number of degrees of freedom (**st/sv**). The number of the degree of freedom event, the first period of the exchange phase: $((A+B)/A)^{-1}$, almost corresponds to the value of the isotope mass event number $m \rightarrow 13^{-1}$. In this case, comparison of these values: [**st/sv** ($0.075759764^{-1} = 13.19961873$) $\leftrightarrow m \rightarrow 13^{-1}$ ($0.076923077^{-1} = 13$)], leads to a discrepancy between the contents of numerical events of the internal and external environment. Subject to the law of conservation of mass, the internal structure "adapts" in the process of phase exchange, due to the distribution of the number of degrees of freedom (**st/sv**) between the periodic limits of the projections of the main functions of the proton and neutron. In contrast to the result of the physical correlations of "short-range forces" of the critical mass, the genetic process of reorientation reproduces division, followed by a chiral type of functionally "mirror" projections of structural values. Here chirality is the posture of projections of functional structures of two periods of reorientation - the act of dividing the internal structure located in the projection of the external environment. The nucleon, the mass number of the event of the degree of freedom (**st/sv**), contains the following information of the cyclic content: [$\sqrt{(13.19961873 / 13)} = 1.007648395$] – two reduced protons. **Table 15(a)** follows.

Table 15(a).

	${}_{-7}N^{13}$			
	$((A+B)/B)^{-1}$			
Pr	$A \rightarrow f mp$	$B \rightarrow f mn$	st/sv	$m \rightarrow 13^{-1}$
1	0.461880832	0.538597739	-0.076716906	0.076923077
2	0.461659895	0.538818676	-0.07715878	0.076923077
3	0.461439064	0.539039507	-0.077600443	0.076923077
4	0.461218338	0.539260233	-0.078041895	0.076923077
5	0.460997718	0.539480853	-0.078483135	0.076923077
679	0.333923992	0.666554579	-0.332630587	0.076923077
680	0.333764262	0.666714309	-0.332950047	0.076923077
681	0.333604608	0.666873963	-0.333269354	0.076923077
682	0.333445031	0.66703354	-0.333588508	0.076923077
683	0.33328553	0.667193041	-0.33390751	0.076923077
684	0.333126106	0.667352465	-0.334226359	0.076923077
685	0.332966758	0.667511813	-0.334545055	0.076923077
686	0.332807486	0.667671085	-0.3348636	0.076923077

Table 15(a), functional exchange phase: $((A+B)/B)^{-1}$, relative to neutron projection.

In this process, the phase of "expansion" occurs - the reproduction of the projection of the proton function, the number of the degree of freedom (**st/sv**). The periods (**679 ↔ 683**) of the function (**A → f mp**) and (**st/sv**) contain polar projections ("heat" and "cold") of the proton function. In the genetic definition, this is the process of "separation" of the organic environment. The range of periods (**679 - 683 = 4**) of this process sets the limits of the formation of the corresponding functional structure of the future organic environment. Thus, the internal organic content reproduces its functional structure of the external content. In this case, the neutron function that separates and combines these organic contents is the projection function of these "polar" values. At the beginning of this material, **table 3** provides the meaning of these definitions in relation to the function of the proton in terms of the Hydrogen "expansion" phase sequence **Table 3**.

For a more detailed understanding of the concept of evolutionary cycles of organic matter, which is in the conditions of functional structures of phase exchanges with periods of opposite variable processes of "compression" and "expansion" where, the reason for the interaction is the process of reorientation of the internal and external content of the functional conditions of the contour of the structure of organic space, the following tables are proposed (**Table 16, 16(a)**).

Table 16.

	${}^2\text{He}^3$					
	$((A+B)/A)^{-1}$					
Pr	A → f mp	B → f mn	st/sv	m → 3⁻¹	fmp'	fmn'
1	0.666360472	0.334289528	0.33207094	0.3333	0.5002298	0.9971396
2	0.665927619	0.334722381	0.33120524	0.3333	0.5005549	0.9958501
3	0.665495047	0.335154953	0.33034009	0.3333	0.5008803	0.9945648
4	0.665062756	0.335587244	0.32947551	0.3333	0.5012058	0.9932837
5	0.664630746	0.336019254	0.32861149	0.3333	0.5015316	0.9920066
6	0.664199017	0.336450983	0.32774803	0.3333	0.5018576	0.9907337
438	0.501635143	0.499014857	0.00262029	0.3333	0.6644936	0.6679828
439	0.501309292	0.499340708	0.00196858	0.3333	0.6649255	0.6675469
440	0.500983653	0.499666347	0.00131731	0.3333	0.6653577	0.6671118
441	0.500658225	0.499991775	0.00066645	0.3333	0.6657902	0.6666776
442	0.500333008	0.500316992	1.6017E-05	0.3333	0.666223	0.6662443
443	0.500008003	0.500641997	-0.000634	0.3333	0.666656	0.6658118
444	0.499683209	0.500966791	-0.0012836	0.3333	0.6670893	0.6653801
445	0.499358626	0.501291374	-0.0019327	0.3333	0.6675229	0.6649493
446	0.499034254	0.501615746	-0.0025815	0.3333	0.6679568	0.6645193
447	0.498710092	0.501939908	-0.0032298	0.3333	0.668391	0.6640901
448	0.498386141	0.502263859	-0.0038777	0.3333	0.6688254	0.6636618
449	0.498062401	0.502587599	-0.0045252	0.3333	0.6692602	0.6632343

Table 16. The result of the process of reorientation of Helium (${}^3_2\text{He}$) - the product of the expansion process of Hydrogen (H^3). Only the first five periods and the periods of reorientation (**442 * 443**) are presented, the result of the limits of which: (**1.6017E-05** and **-0.000634**).

This cycle consists in the fact that the "limit" of the displacement posture in the functional structure of Helium, relative to the state of the functional exchange phase: $((\text{A}+\text{B})/\text{A})^{-1}$, projects the "critical" asymmetry of the projections of the main functions, the reduced proton and neutron as part of the structure of its nucleon number. As a result, the exchange functions of proton and neutron projections in periods: (**442** \leftrightarrow **443**) form the maximum equal values of these projections. These data "return" the given projections into the content of "stable" values.

The entire "contour" of the structure of the reorientation process corresponds to the sum of the periods: (**442 + 443 = 885**), the number of events: ($n/s = 885^{-1} = 0.001129944$). The sum of reorientation values: [$n/s \rightarrow (-0.000634 + 1.6017\text{E}-05) = 0.000617977$], corresponds to the event number (n/s) of the Oxygen (${}^{16}_8\text{O}$) neutron. The difference between these values is the number of Helium (${}^3_2\text{He}$) nucleon events: (**0.0006501**). In practice, the result of the reorientation process returns the content of this exchange phase to its original state relative to the main function of this interaction.

Table 16(a).

	${}^3_2\text{He}$					
	$((\text{A}+\text{B})/\text{B})^{-1}$					
Pr	$\text{A} \rightarrow \text{fmp}$	$\text{B} \rightarrow \text{fmn}$	st/sv	$\text{m} \rightarrow 3^{-1}$	fmp'	fmn'
1	0.33363953	0.667010472	-0.33337094	0.3333	0.999082258	0.49974228
2	0.3334228	0.667227196	-0.33380439	0.3333	0.999731661	0.49957996
3	0.33320622	0.66744378	-0.33423756	0.3333	1.000381487	0.49941784
4	0.33298978	0.667660224	-0.33467045	0.3333	1.001031735	0.49925594
5	0.33277347	0.667876526	-0.33510305	0.3333	1.001682405	0.49909425
6	0.33255731	0.668092689	-0.33553538	0.3333	1.002333499	0.49893277
438	0.25116333	0.749486674	-0.49832335	0.3333	1.327157663	0.44474885
439	0.25100018	0.749649824	-0.49864965	0.3333	1.328020316	0.44465205
440	0.25083713	0.749812868	-0.49897574	0.3333	1.328883529	0.44455537
441	0.25067419	0.749975806	-0.49930161	0.3333	1.329747303	0.44445878
442	0.25051136	0.750138638	-0.49962728	0.3333	1.330611639	0.4443623
443	0.25034863	0.750301365	-0.49995273	0.3333	1.331476536	0.44426593
444	0.25018601	0.750463986	-0.50027797	0.3333	1.332341996	0.44416966
445	0.2500235	0.750626501	-0.500603	0.3333	1/333208018	0.44407349
446	0.24986109	0.750788911	-0.50092782	0.3333	1.334074604	0.44397743
447	0.24969878	0.750951215	-0.50125243	0.3333	1.334941752	0.44388148
448	0.24953659	0.751113414	-0.50157683	0.3333	1.335809464	0.44378562
449	0.24937449	0.751275507	-0.50190101	0.3333	1.33667774	0.44368987

Table 16(a). The phase of functional exchange relative to the neutron fragment: $[\frac{(A+B)}{B}]^{-1}$. There is no reorientation here, no division and multiplication of functional projections. Here is a demonstration of the content of the functional structure, the complex limits of the composition of projections. Here, quantitative structures of periodic compositions, their connections, development and transitions are formed and read as a result of this phase of exchange. The connection of three functional arguments: ($A \rightarrow \mathbf{f mp}$, $B \rightarrow \mathbf{f mn}$ and $\mathbf{st/sv}$), of the sixth period, "gradually" turns into the content of the connection of the composition of the four arguments of the four hundred and thirty-eighth period. This is an early functional structure of the protein mutation process. For example, this may contain the composition of four nucleons and the sum of the masses:

$$\bullet [(\mathbf{nykl O} + \mathbf{nykl N} + \mathbf{nykl C} + \mathbf{nykl B}) = \mathbf{nykl'} \rightarrow$$

$$(\mathbf{0.9999625} + \mathbf{1.000478571} + \mathbf{1.000929167} + \mathbf{0.982818182}) = \mathbf{3.98418842}]$$

$$\bullet (\mathbf{12.9995125} + \mathbf{13.00622142} + \mathbf{13.01207917} + \mathbf{12.77663637}) = \mathbf{51.79444946}$$

Here, the number of events:

$$[(\mathbf{n/snykl} = \mathbf{3.98418842}^{-1} = \mathbf{0.250992146}), (\mathbf{n/sm} = \mathbf{51.79444946}^{-1} = \mathbf{0.019307088})]$$

For example, the information of the result, the function of the proton, the first period of interaction of the proton and neutron projections: ($\mathbf{fmp}' = \mathbf{0.5002298}$), contains one second part of the Carbon nucleon: $[(\mathbf{2fmp}')^2 = \mathbf{nyklC}]$.

As you can see, the value of the event number ($\mathbf{n/s}$) of the sum of nucleons coincides with the state number of the proton function in the four hundred thirty-ninth period: $[\mathbf{Pr (439)} \rightarrow \mathbf{0.25100018}]$. Naturally, the selection of more accurate data is decided by the program content of the corresponding database. In an explanatory version, the functional content of this structure is as follows:

Indicative table.

	fmp	fmn	st/cv	M mp	M mn	M	nykl
a	0.250982733	0.745064372	-0.494081638	12.9995125	38.59019894	51.58971144	0.992109835
b	0.251112263	0.744934842	-0.493822579	13.00622142	38.58349002	51.58971144	0.992109835
c	0.251225359	0.744821746	-0.493596387	13.01207917	38.57763227	51.58971144	0.992109835
d	0.246679644	0.749367461	-0.502687817	12.77663637	38.81307507	51.58971144	0.992109835
sum	1	2.98418842	-1.98418842	51.79444946	154.5643963	206.3588458	3.968439342

Each sum of a given composition is divisible by the argument of this composition.

Provided that the number of nucleon of the sum of the composition is a single value, for example:

$$[\text{nykl}' \rightarrow (3.98418842 / 4 = 0.996047105)].$$

$$\text{Or: } [\text{nykl}' \rightarrow (51.79444946 / 52 = 0.996047105)].$$

The information of this "random" number field was already in this material. This is the number of the limit event of the process of "compression" of Oxygen isotopes. In this case, the category of this structure will be follows: $[\text{Ln}(\text{nykl}'^{-1}) \rightarrow 0.003960728]$.

Thus, the opportunity is realized to "decipher" the data content of the four hundred and thirty-ninth period of the neutron phase of the exchange of Helium (${}^3_2\text{He}$) by the following action, an indicative table.

Here: (a, b, c, d) → arguments of the composition of proton and neutron functions: (fmp, fmn). Mass numbers of the corresponding periods of protons and neutrons: (Mmp, Mmn). Total weight: (M). Nucleons of these masses: (nykl).

• a → fmp: = $((m_8\text{O}^{13} + m_7\text{N}^{13} + m_6\text{C}^{13} + m_5\text{B}^{13}) / m_8\text{O}^{13})^{-1} \rightarrow 0.250982733$; fmn = $(\text{nykl} - \text{fmp}) \rightarrow 0.745064372$
• b → fmp: = $((m_8\text{O}^{13} + m_7\text{N}^{13} + m_6\text{C}^{13} + m_5\text{B}^{13}) / m_7\text{N}^{13})^{-1} \rightarrow 0.251112263$; fmn = $(\text{nykl} - \text{fmp}) \rightarrow 0.744934842$
• c → fmp: = $((m_8\text{O}^{13} + m_7\text{N}^{13} + m_6\text{C}^{13} + m_5\text{B}^{13}) / m_6\text{C}^{13})^{-1} \rightarrow 0.251225359$; fmn = $(\text{nykl} - \text{fmp}) \rightarrow 0.744821746$
• d → fmp: = $((m_8\text{O}^{13} + m_7\text{N}^{13} + m_6\text{C}^{13} + m_5\text{B}^{13}) / m_5\text{B}^{13})^{-1} \rightarrow 0.246679644$; fmn = $(\text{nykl} - \text{fmp}) \rightarrow 0.749367461$

As can be seen from the data of the indicative table, there has been a change in the number of the common nucleon. In this case, the reduced nucleon number is in the trend of the "field" of the nucleon number of static Hydrogen: $(\text{nykl}_1\text{H}' \rightarrow 0.992109835^{-1} = 1.0079_{52914})$. These "random" results are coordinated by the set task, as a result of which the functional limits of formations of natural nuclear, genetic structures are determined, given in the conditions of case studies.

In conclusion of this topic, it is necessary to provide a "primary" static state of the limits of the internal and external expression of natural numbers in the structures of these values. These are projections of positive and negative limits, states of "compression" and "expansion", which are in the content of the unity of matter, **Tables 17, 18, 18(a)**.

Tables 17.

<i>The functional structure of each degree of motion in the processes compression and expansion</i>											
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	compres.	expansion
9	0.111111	0.012346	0.001372	0.000152	1.69E-05	1.88E-06	2.09E-07	2.32E-08	2.58117E-09	1.146E-43	1.08E+41
8	0.125	0.015625	0.001953	0.000244	3.05E-05	3.81E-06	4.77E-07	5.96E-08	7.45058E-09	2.3E-41	6.81E+38
7	0.142857	0.020408	0.002915	0.000416	5.95E-05	8.5E-06	1.21E-06	1.73E-07	2.47809E-08	9.35E-39	2.18E+36
6	0.166667	0.027778	0.00463	0.000772	0.000129	2.14E-05	3.57E-06	5.95E-07	9.9229E-08	9.62E-36	2.89E+33
5	0.2	0.04	0.008	0.0016	3.2E-04	6.4E-05	1.3E-05	2.6E-06	5.1E-07	3.52E-32	1.14E+30
4	0.25	0.0625	0.015625	0.003906	0.000977	0.000244	6.1E-05	1.53E-05	3.8147E-06	8.08E-28	7.74E+25
3	0.333333	0.111111	0.037037	0.012346	0.004115	0.001372	0.000457	0.000152	5.08053E-05	3.38E-22	3.28E+20
2	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625	0.03125	0.015625	0.007813	0.003906	0.001953125	2.84E-14	8.8E+12
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 17. Information of the entire structure of numerical events is contained within the limits of "compression" and expansion of the external and internal, vertical and horizontal composition of natural numbers. The bases of each period correspond to the same degree of "transition" - the connection of the entire structure of the period: $[\text{Ln}(\text{compres.}) / \text{Ln}(9^{-1}) = 5.000000116]$. The same is true for the "expansion" limit: $[\text{Ln}(\text{expansion.}) / \text{Ln}(9^{-1}) = -4.7777777778]$.

Table 18.

<i>The degree of movement of each period as part of the overall of the functional structure (compression)</i>									
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9
9	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000116
8	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.999999994
7	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000008
6	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000022
5	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.999999945
4	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	4.999999957
3	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000061
2	45	22.5	15	11.25	9	7.5	6.428571	5.625	5.000000061
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

In this case, the idea of the result of the primitive action of dividing the sum of the composition of a series of nine natural numbers is violated: $(9 / 2 \neq 4.5 = 5?)$. This paradox corresponds to the divergence between arithmetic and mathematics. The arithmetic real result of dividing the number nine contains other information, which will be presented in the description of table 18(a). Filling the matrix structure with a periodic diagonal content of this order results in a "center" of equal abundances separated by a horizontal fifth period (E') **Matrix 4**.

Matrix 4.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	The sum and difference between periods	
A'	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	Sum of period [A']	9
B'	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0		Sum of period [B']	16
C'	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	0			Sum of period [C']	21
D'	4	4	4	4	4	4	0				Sum of period [D']	24
E'	5	5	5	5	5	0					Sum of period [E']	25
F'	6	6	6	6	0						Sum of period [F']	24
G'	7	7	7	0							Sum of period [G']	21
H'	8	8	0								Sum of period [H']	16
I'	9	0									Sum of period [I']	9
J'	0											
	45	36	28	21	15	10	6	3	1	0	Sum of periods	165
	The sum of the end values of the periods											16

Table 18(a).

The degree of movement of each period in the compositions of structures of general functional relations (expansion)									
	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9
9	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777948
8	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777799
7	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777663
6	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777803
5	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777876
4	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777827
3	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777788
2	-43	-21.5	-14.3333	-10.75	-8.60	-7.16667	-6.14286	-5.375	-4.77777723
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Comparison of the provided data tables: **18** and **18(a)**, demonstrates the unity of the polar structures of the static limits, which are in equal periodic values of the "degrees of connection" of these limits. These conditions maximally approximate these compositions of the extreme projections of the "compression" and "expansion" limits.

The sum of these degrees:

$$(-4.77777948 + 5.000000116 = (0.222222063)^{-1} = 4.500003224).$$

Difference: (9.777778064).

In this case, for example, the sum and difference of the periods:

$$(-8): (-5.375 + 5.625) = 0.25 \text{ and } [5.625 - (-5.375)] = 11.$$

These results are substantiated by the general values of the polar limits of "visible" and "invisible" matter.

The nature of the formation of material or global space is in the projection ratio of all possible limits, transformed forms of its content. Its primary state, as the unity of matter, consists of two main functions of the limits of its external and internal content, which are in a constant periodic and cyclic process of their expression. The constancy of this variable state determines the "inconsistency" of the unity of the expression of external and internal matter, contained in its consciousness - a phase that does not have "limits" of its content - a product of variable limits of cyclically transformed forms of its content. This is the consciousness contained in natural numbers - symbols that allow you to operate with phase limits, any material concept of the numerical structures of cyclic contents. This "instrument" of numbers, the structure of which contains "itself in itself", makes it possible to accurately distribute the values of the phase limits of material values in the periods of values of the cyclic structure of the essence of matter. Thus, any state, of any phase limits of matter, contains the primary potential of consciousness - the product of any phase limits. In this case, the formation of a material or global space is given by the initial global consciousness - a matrix that contains the entire Nature of the structure of its cycles.

According to the condition of the assignment, the author does not use dubious terminology and experimental data, popular research concepts, numbers and their results of controversial definitions in various aspects of this topic.

22.06.2023, Novosibirsk, **Russia**.

• Subject material:

•How Certain Nuclei Split[1902.0112v1.pdf](#)

• Taito Murakami et al, High Proton Conductivity in β -Ba₂ScAlO₅ Enabled by Octahedral and Intrinsically Oxygen-Deficient Layers, *Advanced Functional Materials* (2022). DOI: [10.1002/adfm.202206777](https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202206777)

Journal information: [Advanced Functional Materials](#)

• [Elucidating the mechanism of high proton conduction to develop clean energy materials](#)

• [Successful synthesis of rare isotopic atropisomers with high rotational stability \(phys.org\)](#)

• D. Ruth et al, Proton spin structure and generalized polarizabilities in the strong quantum chromodynamics regime, *Nature Physics* (2022). DOI: [10.1038/s41567-022-01781-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-022-01781-y)

Journal information: [Nature Physics](#)

• J. J. Liu et al, Observation of a Strongly Isospin-Mixed Doublet in Si²⁶ via β -Delayed Two-Proton Decay of P²⁶, *Physical Review Letters* (2022). DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevLett.129.242502](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.129.242502)

• Shihao Li et al, Molecule-electron-proton transfer in enzyme-photo-coupled catalytic system, *Chinese Journal of Catalysis* (2022). DOI: [10.1016/S1872-2067\(22\)64154-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-2067(22)64154-8)

• Lukas Reith et al, In Situ Detection of Iron in Oxidation States \geq IV in Cobalt-Iron Oxyhydroxide Reconstructed during Oxygen Evolution Reaction, *Advanced Energy Materials* (2023). DOI: [10.1002/aenm.202203886](https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202203886)

• Seongwook Chae et al, Longitudinally grown pyrolyzed quinacridones for sodium-ion battery anode, *Chemical Engineering Journal* (2022). DOI: [10.1016/j.cej.2022.139805](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.139805)

• Jixin Yan et al, Recent progress in carbon-based electrochemical catalysts: From structure design to potential applications, *Nano Research Energy* (2022). DOI: [10.26599/NRE.2023.9120047](https://doi.org/10.26599/NRE.2023.9120047)

• [Nucleon tensor charge from exclusive \$\pi^0\$ electroproduction](#)

• [Nucleon Tensor Charge from Exclusive \$\pi^0\$ Electroproduction](#)

• [A New Perspective on Parton Distributions in Nuclei](#)

• [Connection between In Medium Nucleon Form Factors and Deep Inelastic Structure Functions](#)

• [Quantum computer race intensifies as alternative technology gains steam \(nature.com\)](#)

• [Physicists create long-sought topological quantum states](#)

• [Creation of Non-Abelian Topological Order and Anyons on a Trapped-Ion Processor](#) (2023).

Mohsin Iqbal, Nathanan Tantivasadakarn, Ruben Verresen, Sara L. Campbell, Joan M. Dreiling, Caroline Figgatt, John P. Gaebler, Jacob Johansen, Michael Mills, Steven A. Moses, Juan M. Pino, Anthony Ransford, Mary Rowe, Peter Siegfried, Russell P. Stutz, Michael Foss-Feig, Ashv